

Quality of Life in Oncology:
measuring what matters for
cancer patients and survivors
in Europe

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EUonQoL

Quality of Life in Oncology: measuring what matters for cancer patients and survivors in Europe

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Preface

This report is written as a product of the project “Quality of Life in Oncology: measuring what matters for cancer patients and survivors in Europe (EUonQoL)”. This project is funded by the European Union.

The strict collaboration with the Grant Office IEO provided us valuable feedback, particularly we would like to thank Dr. Elena Dal Zotto and Dr. Ilaria Foti. Their input and suggestions made it possible for us to incorporate their expertise and perspective from the beginning of our tasks. Furthermore, we would like to thank our translation providers for their external services and for their expertise in cultural adaptation and all the clinical centers who collaborated with IEO Team in the preliminary translations.

Also, IEO team would like to thank the EUonQoL Executive Committee for providing us with input on the tasks, roles, and responsibilities, as well as co-researchers involved in this process (Carina Dantas and Laura Pinnavaia).

The authors would like to thank WP3 partners (with particular regard on EORTC group) and WP4 for the collaboration within Task 5.3 of the EUonQoL project.

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1. Introduction

The first part of the present report will provide an overview of the EUonQoL project within which this report is situated. Additionally, it will introduce and outline the objectives and contents of the present report. Subsequently, next paragraphs will present and delineate methodologies followed to reach the aim of task 5.3 and the material used to keep track of it. In the final part of the report, conclusions are presented.

This WP is part of an EU funded project entitled “EUonQoL-Quality of Life in Oncology: measuring what matters for cancer patients and survivors in Europe” (grant agreement n° 101096362).

The overall project aims to develop, pilot and validate the European Oncology Quality of Life toolkit (EUonQoL-Kit), a patient co-researcher driven, unified system for the assessment of quality of life (QoL) based on the evaluations and preferences of cancer patients (ongoing treatment, palliative care) and survivors. The EUonQoL-Kit has been developed from the patient perspective, administered digitally, and will be available in all 27 European Union (EU) and associated countries languages.

1.1. The EUonQoL project

Cancer is the second cause of death and the first cause of suffering for patients and caregivers in Europe, as well as having an enormous financial impact on health services and individuals. There were 2.7 million new cases of cancer and 1.3 million deaths in 2020, which is expected to increase with about 25% by 2035. Additionally, there is an unacceptable variability in terms of access to innovation, quality of care, and outcomes (including QoL), within and between countries in Europe. QoL can be interpreted as satisfaction and happiness measured as the achievement of aspirations and/or the realization of individual expectations. The burden of cancer and cancer treatment on QoL is well-recognized. Nonetheless, implementation of QoL assessment in routine oncology practice is not yet part of standard of care. In the same way, health care systems and cancer control programs do not take into consideration QoL measures when developing clinical, societal, and healthcare policymaking systems.

Emerging needs related to new cancer treatments along with societal developments require a revision of traditional QoL assessment tools, most of which have been developed a few decades ago and are not available in all official and non-official European languages.

Available questionnaires are often “static”, presenting the same set of questions/items to all patients, without any difference. Recent innovation in the assessment of HRQoL (Health-Related Quality of Life) in cancer is the development of the Computer-Adaptive Testing (CAT). CAT allows for a more precise assessment of HRQoL, with systems presenting subsequent questions based on answers to the previous ones, ultimately adapting the questions to the health state of the individual patient. In addition, most existing HRQoL tools were developed to be filled out through paper and pencil. These tools will in turn allow for more dynamic instruments, suitable for a personalized patient’s experience of data collection. The overall project process wants to ensure that the EUonQoL-Kit and its future development would be a unified, standard European QoL assessment system. For the aforementioned reasons significant focus was directed towards the translation process, in order to ensure a consistently high standard of translated materials and to cover both linguistic and cultural diversity across Europe.

In Table 1 all WPs involved in the project are presented.

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Table 1: Work packages of the EUonQoL EU project

Work Package	WP Title
WP1	Ethics
WP2	Involvement of stakeholders and patients
WP3	Review of existing HRQoL databases, measures and item libraries
WP4	Development of the EUonQoL-Kit
WP5	Cross-cultural determinants of the QoL and linguistic and cultural adaptation of EUonQoL-Kit
WP6	Digital tools for data collection
WP7	EUonQoL-Kit Pilot Survey
WP8	Implementation
WP9	Dissemination
WP10	Project Management/Coordination

To gain a better understanding of the process utilized in the EUonQoL project, refer to Figure 1, which depicts the flow diagram illustrating the involved Work Packages and their connections.

Figure 1: Flow diagram of project

1.1.1. Population: Active treatment, Survivors, Palliative Care

The aim of the EUonQoL-Kit is to reflect the spectrum of patients diagnosed with cancer. The questionnaires will be administered and validated in three different cancer groups: active treatment, survivors, and palliative care. The definitions outlined within the project might not be exhaustive of the whole cancer patient population, but they are essential to validate the tool and to be able to distinguish three different patient groups with relative precision. As agreed with the EUonQoL Consortium, the target population groups are defined throughout all stages of this study as:

Group A. Active Treatment:

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i. curative treatment - undergoing or recently completed curative treatment for early-stage cancers.

Examples: - Early stage 1-2 breast cancer during or up to 3 months following radiotherapy, surgery or systemic treatments.

ii. non-curative treatment for advanced/metastatic cancers, including disease controlling/life prolonging tumour-directed treatment (e.g. patients with metastatic disease receiving chemotherapy, immunotherapy or targeted agents).

Examples: - *Metastatic breast cancer on 1st line palliative chemotherapy;* - *Lung cancer on immunotherapy.*

Group B. Survivors:

i. At least one year off active treatment (but can be on long-term adjuvant hormonal therapy) and being disease-free without evidence of active cancer. We will aim to recruit survivors >5 years.

Examples: - *ER/PR+ breast cancer treated with surgery, adjuvant radiotherapy and on 10 years of hormonal treatment.*

Group C. Palliative Care: Patients with advanced cancers who meet at least one of the following criteria:

i. Patients with projected prognosis ≤ 70 or ECOG ≤ 2 .

ii. Patients referred to a specialist palliative care team for symptom control.

iii. Patients may be receiving non-curative treatment purely for symptom control (including palliative radiotherapy and/or systemic treatment).

Examples: - *Patients with castrate-resistant prostate cancer, progressed through systemic treatment options referred for radiotherapy for bone pain;* - *Metastatic breast cancer patient on 5th line systemic treatment.*

1.1. Aim of the Report

The principal aim of Task 5.3 is to provide high-quality translations and cultural adaptation of the newly developed EUonQoL-Kit to support comparability of survey results across European languages of involved countries. With the present report IEO team wants to highlight its coordination process after the selection of the two most suitable providers for high-quality translation services to reach the goal of the translation and cultural adaptation of the EUonQoL-Kit.

IEO, as Task Leader, together with the other involved clinical centers, worked to address the aim of incorporation and validation in the translated EUonQoL-Kit of cultural elements of the target patients in order to improve their attitudes toward the intervention. In Table 2 all the clinical centers that conducted the preliminary translations of the Toolkit are presented.

Table 2: Eight clinical centers that conducted the preliminary translations of the Toolkit

COUNTRY	CENTRE NAME	ACRONYM
UK	Leeds Cancer Centre	LEEDS
IT	Fondazione IRCCS Istituto Nazionale Tumori-Milano	INT
FR	Institut Gustave Roussy	GR
FR	Institut Curie	CURIE
NL	Netherlands Cancer Institute	NKI
DE	German Cancer Research Center	DKFZ
DK	Rigshospitalet, Copenhagen	RH
DK	Bispebjerg Hospital, Copenhagen	BH

Finally, IEO analyzed and summarized the provided translations and sent them to WP6 for the digitalization of the contents and to WP7 for the multi-centred EUonQoL-Kit Pilot survey.

2. Methodology

To fulfill the aim of Task 5.3, several methodological steps were followed.

Firstly, IEO supervised the preliminary translation of the EUonQoL-Kit into six languages, including the starting version in English (Danish, Dutch, French, German, Italian); these six translations were internally performed in different clinical centers. The aim of this first step was to allow an initial setting of the Mobile App interfaced with the web-based platform and generate a first draft of the graphical visualization of EUonQoL on the devices. IEO addressed this aim with a strict coordination with WP6 (Leader: DIGICORE) also in order to set-up the conduction of the multi-centered Pilot survey with the final version of the EUonQoL-Kit.

Subsequently, the EUonQoL-Kit developed in English has been translated into the 24 European official languages (Bulgarian, Croatian, Czech, Danish, Dutch, English, Estonian, Finnish, French, German, Greek, Hungarian, Irish, Italian, Latvian, Lithuanian, Maltese, Polish, Portuguese, Romanian, Slovak, Slovenian, Spanish, Swedish) and 7 non-official languages spoken in the associated countries involved in the project (Albanian, Georgian, Moldovan, Norwegian, Serbian, Turkish, Ukrainian).

To perform this activity, IEO was in charge of selecting one or more suitable provider(s) for the best translation service. After the identification of the translation agencies, IEO continuously interacted with the identified contractors to oversee the entire process and monitor that the providers followed the specified steps to reach the aim of the translation and cultural adaptation of the EUonQoL-Kit. Specifically, the translation and cultural adaptation process followed the ISPOR Guidelines, ensuring forward-backward translations and cognitive debriefing. Both translations and debriefing interviews were performed by professional translation agencies as external services providers with experience in PROMs (Patient-

reported outcome measures) and cultural adaptation methods; these actions were supervised by IEO team, in order to guarantee an adequate high-quality result.

Finally, IEO collected all the provided reports to summarize the entire translation and cultural adaptation process and patients' feedback received during the cognitive debriefing.

In the next paragraphs, a detailed description of each of the listed steps is provided.

2.1. Preliminary six translations performed internally

Preliminary translations were carried out by research centers participating in the EUonQoL project, having fluency and good understanding in both the source language (English) and the targeted one (which was one of the following: Danish, Dutch, French, German, Italian).

Additionally, the internal translator was required to show a good expertise and knowledge in not only the two languages (origin/source and target), but also a profound understanding of various aspects associated with QoL in cancer patients and the progression of their disease.

Please See Appendix for more details.

2.2. Translation and Cultural Adaptation (TCA) process

The Translation and Cultural Adaptation (TCA) of the EUonQoL-Kit has been completed for all new items, following the ISPOR (International Society for Pharmacoeconomics and Outcomes Research) translation and cultural adaptation guidelines (Wild et al., 2005) and the listed below steps to assess the comprehensibility of the EUonQoL-Kit. The TCA Group formed by ISPOR, developed the Principles of Good Practice (PGP), a report on current methods to be followed during TCA of PROMs.

IEO team placed significant emphasis on overseeing the entire translation process to guarantee a consistent high quality of translated questionnaires.

In order to adhere to TCA guidelines, the subsequent steps were executed:

Step 1: Forward translation/; it is the initial step that occurs after the preparation of items and corresponds to the translation of the English original version (i.e. the source language) into another language (i.e. target language). The translations were performed by two specialized translators who are native speakers of the target language, after the conceptualization of the entire text provided in the EUonQoL-Kit.

Step 2: Reconciliation; in this phase, various translations are compared and merged into a single forward translation; the reconciliation has been performed by a third person to reach the best possible version. After a consensus has been reached between all translators involved.

Step 3: Backward translation; this phase involves the translation from the target language back into the original one, which in this case was English.

Step 4: Harmonization; which is the comparison of back translations of different language versions among themselves and with the original instrument, in order to highlight discrepancies between the original and its derivative translations, as well as to establish a single approach to addressing translation issues, that is essential to inter-translation validity.

Step 5: Cognitive Debriefing (CD); this phase involves testing the instrument on a small group of five cancer patients. The purpose is to evaluate rewordings and to assess the understandability, interpretation, and cultural relevance of each individual translation;

Step 6: Review of CD; at this stage of the process, the outcomes of the CD are compared with the original version of the questionnaire. This process is important to assure cultural relevance of the translation.

Step 7: Proofreading; this step entails the final review of the translation to focus on any typographic, grammatical or other errors and to make any necessary corrections.

Step 8: Final report; a report is generated at the end of the translation process to document the development of each translation and to ensure the quality of the entire process.

Finally, IEO analyzed and summarized the results and the translations in order to pass them to WP6 for the digitalization of the contents and to give some feedback to WP7 for the multicentered EUonQoL-Kit Pilot survey.

2.3. Timelines of TCA process

The TCA process started in mid-January 2024 to March 2024, following a strict coordination between WP4, WP5 and EORTC Group. This collaboration aimed to develop an Excel file which would serve as a shared resource for the selected providers. The primary objective during this phase was to streamline the translation process itself, ensuring efficiency and accuracy in rendering the content of the EUonQoL-Kit into various languages. It is noteworthy that a significant number of core domains items used in the EUonQoL-Kit were already available in most of official and non-official European languages (as the EORTC-QOL Group has an extensive Item library containing validated items and their corresponding translations. By February 2024, this valuable resource had been made accessible to WP5 by EORTC Group, further facilitating the translation process.

This decision was motivated by the aim of accelerating the translation process and mitigate the risk of potential overlap or discrepancies between the EORTC versions and those produced by our chosen providers. During this phase, WP5 team manually retrieved available translations in all EU languages. This activity highlighted the overlapping Turkish translation of both items “Have you felt miserable?” and “Have you felt helpless?” in the item bank (“*Kendinizi çaresiz hissettiğiniz oldu mu?*”), thus leading to the need to reassess the already available translation; this decision was previously discussed and agreed with the EORTC Group.

The secondary phase was characterized by the **conceptualization** of all the terms used in all the items; the conceptualization is defined as the process of understanding and interpreting concepts, ideas, or terms within the context of a specific language or culture. This involves ensuring that the meaning and intent of the original content (in the source language) are accurately conveyed in the translated version with the target language, considering linguistic nuances, cultural sensitivities, and terminological differences. Conceptualization is crucial for producing translations that are not only linguistically accurate but also contextually appropriate and effective in communicating the intended message to the target audience.

IEO played a pivotal role in facilitating collaboration between translation agencies and WP4, even ensuring a thorough conceptualization process essential for the preparation of translations. Specifically, each item underwent a meticulous definition process, supplemented by explanations through the use of synonyms. This approach aimed to enhance clarity and precision in the translated versions, closely aligning with the standards outlined by ISPOR guidelines for linguistic validation and with the translations used by EORTC Group. Particularly, translators focused their conceptualization on Turkish, Slovak,

Georgian, and Greek. In the following paragraph, some items will be illustrated that, when translated into the aforementioned target languages, sparked debate during the conceptualization phase, as certain terms needed to be culturally adapted during the Cognitive Debriefing phase.

Of note, one of the translation agencies encountered certain obstacles in recruiting cancer patients in Malta due to the country's limited size. Despite this challenge, the agency diligently addressed the issue in a timely manner. The IEO team closely monitored this situation to ensure meticulous oversight of each stage of the process

2.4. Specific Items and terms

2.4.1. Items “Did you worry?” and “Have you felt afraid?” in Slovak

Noteworthy, the item “*Did you worry?*” from target language to Slovak was changed; indeed, the EORTC translation “*Mali ste pocit strachu?*” was modified in “*Pocitovali ste obav?*” in order to accentuate the experience of anxiety more prominently because its meaning is “*Have you felt fear?*” and to distinguish this item from the other item: “*Have you felt afraid?*”, translated as “*Cítili ste strach?*”. This change was necessary to prevent potential clashes between the two items.

During the Cognitive Debriefing patients were tested with both versions “*Mali ste pocit strachu?*” and “*Pocitovali ste obav?*” for the item “*Did you worry?*”, and basically the respondents found the new wording to be slightly clearer as follows: R1: *If I felt anxious; I understand both questions, however, the second one is more natural to me*, R2: *If I felt some fear; I understand both questions and both are equal to me*, R3: *If I had some worries; I understand both questions, however, the second one sounds more natural for me*, R4: *If I felt some worries; I understand both questions and both sound equally to me*, R5: *If I was worried; I understand both questions and I do not know which one is better. They both mean the same to me.*

Regarding the item “*Have you felt afraid?*” respondents reported no difficulties in understanding this item and did not suggest anything for rewording it: R1: *If I felt fear*, R2: *Whether I was afraid of something*, R3: *If I felt fear*, R4: *Whether I felt too scared*, R5: *If I felt hopeless and really afraid.*

2.4.2. Item “Did you feel depressed?” in Georgian

Also, the item “*Did you feel depressed?*” translated in Georgian as “*გრძნობდით დეპრესიას?*”, which included the meaning of clinical depression, raised some issues and EORTC group suggested to the translation agency to ask Mapi (who performed their translations in 2013) to look into their files in order to understand why this item was translated in this way. The Cognitive Debriefing process confirmed that the translation provided with “*გრძნობდით დეპრესიას?*” was suitable as it was understood as follows by the respondents: R1: *Were you in a depressed mood?*, R2: *Have you felt sad, full of sorrow, or hopeless?*, R3: *Did you feel sad and downhearted?*, R4: *Did you feel overwhelmed by your problems?*, R5: *Depressed means when nothing can cheer you up, and you feel pessimistic.*

2.4.3. Item “Have you lacked appetite?” in Greek

The question “*Have you lacked appetite?*”, defined as lacking the desire or interest to eat, was modified in Greek from “*Είχατε ανορεξία,*” to “*Είχατε μειωμένη όρεξη,*” in order to trial a new version that omits the term anorexia. It's worth noting that anorexia is a distinct condition from reduced appetite. During the Cognitive Debriefing respondents declared the following meanings:

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R1: it means you stop eating because you have body image issues. Usually adolescent girls get it; R2: if I didn't feel like eating; R3: the psychological disorder of stopping to eat completely; R4: the opposite of bulimia. If you're a cancer patient you can't afford not to eat even if it makes you sick; R5: not feeling like eating much. But chiefly the disorder. For these reasons the final translation was "did you have reduced/decreased appetite?", avoiding the term "anorexia" in Greek version.

2.4.4. Item "Were you short of breath?" in Greek

Moreover, the item "*Were you short of breath?*" was tested both in Greek version "δύσπνοια" (which is the everyday word for this, using no medical terms but meaning "*panting*") and "λαχανιάσατε;" which means being out of breath. The decision of testing with patients both versions followed the reasoning that "*being short of breath*" and "*to pant*" are referred to two different mechanisms in English: although the action of panting may refer to being short of breath, the cause of this mechanism is often different: because "*to pant*" is what is done after strenuous physical exertion. The agency decided to make the participants choose the best suitable and understandable. The Cognitive Debriefing output were the following: *R1: was it difficult for me to breath? R2: it means you can't breathe properly; R3: difficulty breathing.*

Regarding the phrase "Είχατε δύσπνοια;" it was highlighted that dyspnea may ensue even in a state of calm and repose, without physical exercises or strenuous activities, and was chosen as final version for the Greek translation.

2.4.5. Item "Have you been satisfied with your communication with your professional(s)?" in Greek

The source item "Have you been satisfied with your communication with your professional(s)" was challenging for Greek translators because the version provided by EORTC item bank "Εχετε μείνει ικανοποιημένος/η από την επικοινωνία σας με τον (τους) επαγγελματία(ες);" included the term "professionals" which in Greek means any healthcare providers. Indeed, during the Cognitive Debriefing, patients asked the following clarifications: *R1: what professionals?; R2: I don't understand; R3: professional what? Is this a translation of "professionals"? This is so bad! It's not correct in Greek; R4 I don't understand what professionals are you talking about?; R5: this doesn't make sense to me. I don't know whom you are referring to.* For these reasons, the translation agency provided the translation using the term "health professionals".

The linguistic validation was performed from 10 to 24 April 2024 and the translation agency's team is planning to provide the rationale in the linguistic validation reports by 07May2024.

2.5. Translation agencies' reports

2.5.1. Albanian Linguistic Validation Certificate

LINGUISTIC VALIDATION CERTIFICATE

EUonQoL v2.0 (EUonQoL v2.0)

This is to certify that **ICON Language Services** conducted the linguistic validation of the Electronic version of the EUonQoL v2.0 (source file name: English (UK)_EUonQoL Toolkit V2.0) into Albania - Albanian.

The aim of linguistic validation is to obtain translations that are:

- conceptually equivalent to the original and comparable across languages
- culturally relevant to the context of the target country
- easily understood by the people to whom the translated instrument is administered.

This is achieved using a rigorous ISO-17100 certified methodology¹ involving:

- a process which comprises several steps
- the instrument's developer input on conceptual issues
- a skilled team recruited by **ICON Language Services** in the target country and headed by a consultant with knowledge of and experience in the field of Clinical Outcome Assessments. The consultant supervises and coordinates the linguistic validation process in his/her country
- a centralized review process coordinated by **ICON Language Services**, including quality control by linguists and discussions about translation decisions with the consultant at each step of the process.
- cross-cultural harmonisation to ensure common understanding of the instrument's concepts by all participants involved in the process and achieve conceptual equivalence across languages.

The aforementioned translation (filename : Albanian (Albania)_EUonQoL Toolkit V2_10APR2024, dated 10 April 2024) underwent the following steps:

- Forward Translation step – 2 forward translations by qualified translators and reconciliation
- Backtranslation step – 1 backtranslation by a qualified translator
- Cognitive Interview step:
 - 5 participants; population: Cancer; group: Adults; age range: 25-70
- Proofreading step

ICON Language Services may not be held liable for any changes made on the translation after completion of project **6353-TR-0001** by **ICON Language Services** on **10 April 2024**.

Sébastien Le Dannois
Project Manager
ICON Language Services

Sebastien Le Dannois Sébastien Le Dannois
10 Apr 2024 06:09:57 UTC (Z)

REASON: I approve this document

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¹ References

- Acquadro C., Jambon B., Ellis D. and Marquis P. Language and translation issues. In Spilker B, ed. Quality of Life and Pharmacoeconomics in Clinical Trials. Philadelphia: Lippincott-Raven Publishers, 1996: 575-585. - Linguistic Validation Manual for Health Outcomes Assessments. Acquadro C, Conway K, Giroulet C, Mearl. Second Edition - Mapi Institute, Lyon, France, January 2012 - ISBN: 2-9522021-0-9

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2.5.2. Bulgarian Linguistic Validation Certificate

LINGUISTIC VALIDATION CERTIFICATE

EUonQoL v2.0 (EUonQoL v2.0)

This is to certify that **ICON Language Services** conducted the linguistic validation of the Electronic version of the EUonQoL v2.0 (source file name: English (UK)_EUonQoL Toolkit V2.0) into Bulgaria - Bulgarian.

The aim of linguistic validation is to obtain translations that are:

- conceptually equivalent to the original and comparable across languages
- culturally relevant to the context of the target country
- easily understood by the people to whom the translated instrument is administered.

This is achieved using a rigorous ISO-17100 certified methodology¹ involving:

- a process which comprises several steps
- the instrument's developer input on conceptual issues
- a skilled team recruited by **ICON Language Services** in the target country and headed by a consultant with knowledge of and experience in the field of Clinical Outcome Assessments. The consultant supervises and coordinates the linguistic validation process in his/her country
- a centralized review process coordinated by **ICON Language Services**, including quality control by linguists and discussions about translation decisions with the consultant at each step of the process.
- cross-cultural harmonisation to ensure common understanding of the instrument's concepts by all participants involved in the process and achieve conceptual equivalence across languages.

The aforementioned translation (filename : Bulgarian (Bulgaria)_EUonQoL Toolkit V2.0_05APR2024, dated 5 April 2024) underwent the following steps:

- Forward Translation step – 2 forward translations by qualified translators and reconciliation
- Backtranslation step – 1 backtranslation by a qualified translator
- Cognitive Interview step:
 - 5 participants; population: Cancer; group: Adults; age range: 41-70
- Proofreading step

ICON Language Services may not be held liable for any changes made on the translation after completion of project **6353-TR-0001** by **ICON Language Services** on **5 April 2024**.

Cédric Montigny
Project Mgr, PCS
ICON Language Services

Cedric Montigny Cedric Montigny
05 Apr 2024 08:20:10 UTC (Z)

REASON: I approve this document
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¹ References

- Acquadro C., Jambon B., Ellis D. and Marquis P. Language and translation issues. In Spilker B, ed. Quality of Life and Pharmacoeconomics in Clinical Trials. Philadelphia: Lippincott-Raven Publishers, 1996: 575-585. - Linguistic Validation Manual for Health Outcomes Assessments. Acquadro C, Conway K, Giroudet C, Mear I. Second Edition - Mapi Institute, Lyon, France, January 2012 - ISBN: 2-9522021-0-9

<p style="text-align: center;">Funded by the European Union</p>		
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2.5.3. Croatian Linguistic Validation Certificate

LINGUISTIC VALIDATION CERTIFICATE

EUonQoL v2.0 (EUonQoL v2.0)

This is to certify that **ICON Language Services** conducted the linguistic validation of the Electronic version of the EUonQoL v2.0 (source file name: English (UK)_EUonQoL Toolkit V2.0) into Croatia - Croatian.

The aim of linguistic validation is to obtain translations that are:

- conceptually equivalent to the original and comparable across languages
- culturally relevant to the context of the target country
- easily understood by the people to whom the translated instrument is administered.

This is achieved using a rigorous ISO-17100 certified methodology¹ involving:

- a process which comprises several steps
- the instrument's developer input on conceptual issues
- a skilled team recruited by **ICON Language Services** in the target country and headed by a consultant with knowledge of and experience in the field of Clinical Outcome Assessments. The consultant supervises and coordinates the linguistic validation process in his/her country
- a centralized review process coordinated by **ICON Language Services**, including quality control by linguists and discussions about translation decisions with the consultant at each step of the process.
- cross-cultural harmonisation to ensure common understanding of the instrument's concepts by all participants involved in the process and achieve conceptual equivalence across languages.

The aforementioned translation (filename : Croatian (Croatia)_EUonQoL Toolkit V2.0_04APR2024, dated 4 April 2024) underwent the following steps:

- Forward Translation step – 2 forward translations by qualified translators and reconciliation
- Backtranslation step – 1 backtranslation by a qualified translator
- Cognitive Interview step:
 - 5 participants; population: Cancer; group: Adults; age range: 41-70
- Proofreading step

ICON Language Services may not be held liable for any changes made on the translation after completion of project **6353-TR-0001** by **ICON Language Services** on **4 April 2024**.

Cédric Montigny
Project Mgr, PCS
ICON Language Services

Cedric Montigny Cedric Montigny
04 Apr 2024 08:09:08 UTC (Z)
REASON: I approve this document
829116d-199-40f-a222-86-5655181c5

¹ References

- Acquadro C, Jambon B, Ellis D. and Marquis P. Language and translation issues. In Spilker B, ed. Quality of Life and Pharmacoeconomics in Clinical Trials. Philadelphia: Lippincott-Raven Publishers, 1996: 575-585. - Linguistic Validation Manual for Health Outcomes Assessments. Acquadro C, Conway K, Giroudet C, Mear I. Second Edition - Mapi Institute, Lyon, France, January 2012 - ISBN: 2-9522021-0-9

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2.5.4. Czech Linguistic Validation Certificate

LINGUISTIC VALIDATION CERTIFICATE

EUonQoL v2.0 (EUonQoL v2.0)

This is to certify that **ICON Language Services** conducted the linguistic validation of the Electronic version of the EUonQoL v2.0 (source file name: English (UK)_EUonQoL Toolkit V2.0) into Czech Republic - Czech.

The aim of linguistic validation is to obtain translations that are:

- conceptually equivalent to the original and comparable across languages
- culturally relevant to the context of the target country
- easily understood by the people to whom the translated instrument is administered.

This is achieved using a rigorous ISO-17100 certified methodology¹ involving:

- a process which comprises several steps
- the instrument's developer input on conceptual issues
- a skilled team recruited by **ICON Language Services** in the target country and headed by a consultant with knowledge of and experience in the field of Clinical Outcome Assessments. The consultant supervises and coordinates the linguistic validation process in his/her country
- a centralized review process coordinated by **ICON Language Services**, including quality control by linguists and discussions about translation decisions with the consultant at each step of the process.
- cross-cultural harmonisation to ensure common understanding of the instrument's concepts by all participants involved in the process and achieve conceptual equivalence across languages.

The aforementioned translation (filename : Czech (Czech Republic)_EUonQoL Toolkit V2.0_05APR2024, dated 5 April 2024) underwent the following steps:

- Forward Translation step – 2 forward translations by qualified translators and reconciliation
- Backtranslation step – 1 backtranslation by a qualified translator
- Cognitive Interview step:
 - 5 participants; population: Cancer
- Proofreading step

ICON Language Services may not be held liable for any changes made on the translation after completion of project **6353-TR-0001** by **ICON Language Services** on **5 April 2024**.

Alexia Dos Santos Campanha
Project Manager
ICON Language Services

Alexia Dos Santos Campanha
Alexia Dos Santos Campanha
05 Apr 2024 08:36:18 UTC (Z)
REASON: I approve this document
Ba30aac7 6756 9032 bc19 9e9c74319639

¹ References

- Acquadro C, Jambon B, Ellis D. and Marquis P. Language and translation issues. In Spilker B, ed. Quality of Life and Pharmacoeconomics in Clinical Trials. Philadelphia: Lippincott-Raven Publishers, 1996: 575-585. - Linguistic Validation Manual for Health Outcomes Assessments. Acquadro C, Conway K, Giroudet C, Mear I. Second Edition - Mapi Institute, Lyon, France, January 2012 - ISBN: 2-9522021-0-9

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2.5.5. Danish Linguistic Validation Certificate

LINGUISTIC VALIDATION CERTIFICATE

EUonQoL v2.0 (EUonQoL v2.0)

This is to certify that **ICON Language Services** conducted the linguistic validation of the Electronic version of the EUonQoL v2.0 (source file name: English (UK)_EUonQoL Toolkit V2.0) into Denmark - Danish.

The aim of linguistic validation is to obtain translations that are:

- conceptually equivalent to the original and comparable across languages
- culturally relevant to the context of the target country
- easily understood by the people to whom the translated instrument is administered.

This is achieved using a rigorous ISO-17100 certified methodology¹ involving:

- a process which comprises several steps
- the instrument's developer input on conceptual issues
- a skilled team recruited by **ICON Language Services** in the target country and headed by a consultant with knowledge of and experience in the field of Clinical Outcome Assessments. The consultant supervises and coordinates the linguistic validation process in his/her country
- a centralized review process coordinated by **ICON Language Services**, including quality control by linguists and discussions about translation decisions with the consultant at each step of the process.
- cross-cultural harmonisation to ensure common understanding of the instrument's concepts by all participants involved in the process and achieve conceptual equivalence across languages.

The aforementioned translation (filename : Danish (Denmark)_EUonQoL Toolkit V2.0_08APR2024, dated 8 April 2024) underwent the following steps:

- Forward Translation step – 2 forward translations by qualified translators and reconciliation
- Backtranslation step – 1 backtranslation by a qualified translator
- Cognitive Interview step:
 - 5 participants; population: Cancer; group: Adults; age range: 41-80
- Proofreading step

ICON Language Services may not be held liable for any changes made on the translation after completion of project **6353-TR-0001** by **ICON Language Services** on **8 April 2024**.

Caroline Price
Associate project manager
ICON Language Services

Caroline Price Caroline Price
08 Apr 2024 14:11:25 UTC (Z)
REASON: I approve this document

28c32e82_c148_4c3e_990d_cb17260ca13f

¹ References

- Acquadro C, Jambon B, Ellis D. and Marquis P. Language and translation issues. In Spilker B, ed. Quality of Life and Pharmacoeconomics in Clinical Trials. Philadelphia: Lippincott-Raven Publishers, 1996: 575-585. - Linguistic Validation Manual for Health Outcomes Assessments. Acquadro C, Conway K, Giroudet C, Mear I. Second Edition - Mapi Institute, Lyon, France, January 2012 - ISBN: 2-9522021-0-9

<p style="text-align: center;">Funded by the European Union</p>		
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2.5.6. Dutch Linguistic Validation Certificate

LINGUISTIC VALIDATION CERTIFICATE

EUonQoL v2.0 (EUonQoL v2.0)

This is to certify that **ICON Language Services** conducted the linguistic validation of the Electronic version of the EUonQoL v2.0 (source file name: English (UK)_EUonQoL Toolkit V2.0) into Netherlands - Dutch.

The aim of linguistic validation is to obtain translations that are:

- conceptually equivalent to the original and comparable across languages
- culturally relevant to the context of the target country
- easily understood by the people to whom the translated instrument is administered.

This is achieved using a rigorous ISO-17100 certified methodology¹ involving:

- a process which comprises several steps
- the instrument's developer input on conceptual issues
- a skilled team recruited by **ICON Language Services** in the target country and headed by a consultant with knowledge of and experience in the field of Clinical Outcome Assessments. The consultant supervises and coordinates the linguistic validation process in his/her country
- a centralized review process coordinated by **ICON Language Services**, including quality control by linguists and discussions about translation decisions with the consultant at each step of the process.
- cross-cultural harmonisation to ensure common understanding of the instrument's concepts by all participants involved in the process and achieve conceptual equivalence across languages.

The aforementioned translation (filename : Dutch (Netherlands)_EUonQoL Toolkit V2.0_09APR2024, dated 9 April 2024) underwent the following steps:

- Forward Translation step – 2 forward translations by qualified translators and reconciliation
- Backtranslation step – 1 backtranslation by a qualified translator
- Cognitive Interview step:
 - 5 participants; population: Cancer; group: Adults
- Proofreading step

ICON Language Services may not be held liable for any changes made on the translation after completion of project **6353-TR-0001** by **ICON Language Services** on **9 April 2024**.

Agnes Kiss
Project Manager
ICON Language Services

 Agnes Kiss
 09 Apr 2024 21:29:17 UTC (Z)
 REASON: I approve this document
2051593a-3429-4c2a-b6ac-ed9c252188c5

¹ References

- Acquadro C, Jambon B, Ellis D. and Marquis P. Language and translation issues. In Spilker B, ed. Quality of Life and Pharmacoeconomics in Clinical Trials. Philadelphia: Lippincott-Raven Publishers, 1996: 575-585. - Linguistic Validation Manual for Health Outcomes Assessments. Acquadro C, Conway K, Giroudet C, Mear I. Second Edition - Mapi Institute, Lyon, France, January 2012 - ISBN: 2-9522021-0-9

<p style="text-align: center;">Funded by the European Union</p>		
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2.5.7. Estonian Linguistic Validation Certificate

LINGUISTIC VALIDATION CERTIFICATE

EUonQoL v2.0 (EUonQoL v2.0)

This is to certify that **ICON Language Services** conducted the linguistic validation of the Electronic version of the EUonQoL v2.0 (source file name: English (UK)_EUonQoL Toolkit V2.0) into Estonia - Estonian.

The aim of linguistic validation is to obtain translations that are:

- conceptually equivalent to the original and comparable across languages
- culturally relevant to the context of the target country
- easily understood by the people to whom the translated instrument is administered.

This is achieved using a rigorous ISO-17100 certified methodology¹ involving:

- a process which comprises several steps
- the instrument's developer input on conceptual issues
- a skilled team recruited by **ICON Language Services** in the target country and headed by a consultant with knowledge of and experience in the field of Clinical Outcome Assessments. The consultant supervises and coordinates the linguistic validation process in his/her country
- a centralized review process coordinated by **ICON Language Services**, including quality control by linguists and discussions about translation decisions with the consultant at each step of the process.
- cross-cultural harmonisation to ensure common understanding of the instrument's concepts by all participants involved in the process and achieve conceptual equivalence across languages.

The aforementioned translation (filename : Estonian (Estonia)_EUonQoL Toolkit V2.0_09APR2024, dated 9 April 2024) underwent the following steps:

- Forward Translation step – 2 forward translations by qualified translators and reconciliation
- Backtranslation step – 1 backtranslation by a qualified translator
- Cognitive Interview step:
 - 5 participants; population: Cancer; group: Adults
- Proofreading step

ICON Language Services may not be held liable for any changes made on the translation after completion of project **6353-TR-0001** by **ICON Language Services** on **9 April 2024**.

Agnes Kiss
Project Manager
ICON Language Services

 Agnes Kiss
09 Apr 2024 21:29:16 UTC (Z)
REASON: I approve this document
2051592a 3429 1c2a b6ac cdf9c232188c1

¹ References

- Acquadro C., Jambon B., Ellis D. and Marquis P. Language and translation issues. In Spilker B, ed. Quality of Life and Pharmacoeconomics in Clinical Trials. Philadelphia: Lippincott-Raven Publishers, 1996: 575-585. - Linguistic Validation Manual for Health Outcomes Assessments. Acquadro C, Conway K, Giroulet C, Mear I. Second Edition - Mapi Institute, Lyon, France, January 2012 - ISBN: 2-9522021-0-9

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2.5.8. Finnish Linguistic Validation Certificate

LINGUISTIC VALIDATION CERTIFICATE

EUonQoL v2.0 (EUonQoL v2.0)

This is to certify that **ICON Language Services** conducted the linguistic validation of the Electronic version of the EUonQoL v2.0 (source file name: English (UK)_EUonQoL Toolkit V2.0) into Finland - Finnish.

The aim of linguistic validation is to obtain translations that are:

- conceptually equivalent to the original and comparable across languages
- culturally relevant to the context of the target country
- easily understood by the people to whom the translated instrument is administered.

This is achieved using a rigorous ISO-17100 certified methodology¹ involving:

- a process which comprises several steps
- the instrument's developer input on conceptual issues
- a skilled team recruited by **ICON Language Services** in the target country and headed by a consultant with knowledge of and experience in the field of Clinical Outcome Assessments. The consultant supervises and coordinates the linguistic validation process in his/her country
- a centralized review process coordinated by **ICON Language Services**, including quality control by linguists and discussions about translation decisions with the consultant at each step of the process.
- cross-cultural harmonisation to ensure common understanding of the instrument's concepts by all participants involved in the process and achieve conceptual equivalence across languages.

The aforementioned translation (filename : Finnish (Finland)_EUonQoL Toolkit V2.0_10APR2024, dated 10 April 2024) underwent the following steps:

- Forward Translation step – 2 forward translations by qualified translators and reconciliation
- Backtranslation step – 1 backtranslation by a qualified translator
- Cognitive Interview step:
 - 5 participants; population: Cancer; group: Adults
- Proofreading step

ICON Language Services may not be held liable for any changes made on the translation after completion of project **6353-TR-0001** by **ICON Language Services** on **10 April 2024**.

Becki Ellsmore
Associate Project Manager
ICON Language Services

Becki Ellsmore
10 Apr 2024 14:16:23 UTC (Z)
REASON: I approve this document
d779d241b-27af-48ab-963c-ac7accd28f7a

¹ References

- Acquadro C, Jambon B., Ellis D. and Marquis P. Language and translation issues. In Spilker B, ed. Quality of Life and Pharmacoeconomics in Clinical Trials. Philadelphia: Lippincott-Raven Publishers, 1996: 575-585. - Linguistic Validation Manual for Health Outcomes Assessments. Acquadro C, Conway K, Giroudet C, Mear I. Second Edition - Mapi Institute, Lyon, France, January 2012 - ISBN: 2-9522021-0-9

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2.5.9. French Linguistic Validation Certificate

LINGUISTIC VALIDATION CERTIFICATE

EUonQoL v2.0 (EUonQoL v2.0)

This is to certify that **ICON Language Services** conducted the linguistic validation of the Electronic version of the EUonQoL v2.0 (source file name: English (UK)_EUonQoL Toolkit V2.0) into France - French.

The aim of linguistic validation is to obtain translations that are:

- conceptually equivalent to the original and comparable across languages
- culturally relevant to the context of the target country
- easily understood by the people to whom the translated instrument is administered.

This is achieved using a rigorous ISO-17100 certified methodology¹ involving:

- a process which comprises several steps
- the instrument's developer input on conceptual issues
- a skilled team recruited by **ICON Language Services** in the target country and headed by a consultant with knowledge of and experience in the field of Clinical Outcome Assessments. The consultant supervises and coordinates the linguistic validation process in his/her country
- a centralized review process coordinated by **ICON Language Services**, including quality control by linguists and discussions about translation decisions with the consultant at each step of the process.
- cross-cultural harmonisation to ensure common understanding of the instrument's concepts by all participants involved in the process and achieve conceptual equivalence across languages.

The aforementioned translation (filename : French (France)_EUonQoL Toolkit V2.0_02APR2024, dated 2 April 2024) underwent the following steps:

- Forward Translation step – 2 forward translations by qualified translators and reconciliation
- Backtranslation step – 1 backtranslation by a qualified translator
- Cognitive Interview step:
 - 5 participants; population: Cancer; group: Adults; age range: 31-70
- Proofreading step

ICON Language Services may not be held liable for any changes made on the translation after completion of project **6353-TR-0001** by **ICON Language Services** on **2 April 2024**.

Clemence Gallud
Project Coordinator
ICON Language Services

¹ References

- Acquadro C, Jambon B., Ellis D. and Marquis P. Language and translation issues. In Spilker B, ed. Quality of Life and Pharmacoeconomics in Clinical Trials. Philadelphia: Lippincott-Raven Publishers, 1996: 575-585. - Linguistic Validation Manual for Health Outcomes Assessments. Acquadro C, Conway K, Giroudet C, Mear I. Second Edition - Mapi Institute, Lyon, France, January 2012 - ISBN: 2-9522021-0-9

Clemence Gallud Clemence Gallud
02 Apr 2024 08:58:34 UTC (Z)

REASON: I approve this document

c5240128 9d80 4319 bc5c 89c92cb8c284

EUonQoL v2.0_France/French - Version of 02 Apr 2024 - ICON
ID6353-TR-0001 / French (France)_EUonQoL Toolkit V2.0_02APR2024.CoT

DocUID : 2066366-006c-486d-bd01-2c15ae602d45

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2.5.10. Georgian Linguistic Validation Certificate

LINGUISTIC VALIDATION CERTIFICATE

EUonQoL v2.0 (EUonQoL v2.0)

This is to certify that **ICON Language Services** conducted the linguistic validation of the Electronic version of the EUonQoL v2.0 (source file name: English (UK)_EUonQoL Toolkit V2.0) into Georgia - Georgian.

The aim of linguistic validation is to obtain translations that are:

- conceptually equivalent to the original and comparable across languages
- culturally relevant to the context of the target country
- easily understood by the people to whom the translated instrument is administered.

This is achieved using a rigorous ISO-17100 certified methodology¹ involving:

- a process which comprises several steps
- the instrument's developer input on conceptual issues
- a skilled team recruited by **ICON Language Services** in the target country and headed by a consultant with knowledge of and experience in the field of Clinical Outcome Assessments. The consultant supervises and coordinates the linguistic validation process in his/her country
- a centralized review process coordinated by **ICON Language Services**, including quality control by linguists and discussions about translation decisions with the consultant at each step of the process.
- cross-cultural harmonisation to ensure common understanding of the instrument's concepts by all participants involved in the process and achieve conceptual equivalence across languages.

The aforementioned translation (filename : Georgian (Georgia)_EUonQoL Toolkit V2.0_03APR2024, dated 3 April 2024) underwent the following steps:

- Forward Translation step – 2 forward translations by qualified translators and reconciliation
- Backtranslation step – 1 backtranslation by a qualified translator
- Cognitive Interview step:
 - 5 participants; population: Cancer; group: Adults; age range: 18-80+
- Proofreading step

ICON Language Services may not be held liable for any changes made on the translation after completion of project **6353-TR-0001** by **ICON Language Services** on **3 April 2024**.

Veronica Gonzalez De La Rosa
Project Manager
ICON Language Services

Veronica Gonzalez de la Rosa Veronica Gonzalez de la Rosa
04 Apr 2024 15:13:14 UTC (Z)
REASON: I approve this document
e9db16af 2af0 4382 9acd 6157219b289

¹ References

- Acquadro C, Jambon B, Ellis D. and Marquis P. Language and translation issues. In Spilker B, ed. Quality of Life and Pharmacoeconomics in Clinical Trials. Philadelphia: Lippincott-Raven Publishers, 1996: 575-585. - Linguistic Validation Manual for Health Outcomes Assessments. Acquadro C, Conway K, Giroudet C, Mear I. Second Edition - Mapi Institute, Lyon, France, January 2012 - ISBN: 2-9522021-0-9

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2.5.11. German Linguistic Validation Certificate

LINGUISTIC VALIDATION CERTIFICATE

EUonQoL v2.0 (EUonQoL v2.0)

This is to certify that **ICON Language Services** conducted the linguistic validation of the Electronic version of the EUonQoL v2.0 (source file name: English (UK)_EUonQoL Toolkit V2.0) into Germany - German.

The aim of linguistic validation is to obtain translations that are:

- conceptually equivalent to the original and comparable across languages
- culturally relevant to the context of the target country
- easily understood by the people to whom the translated instrument is administered.

This is achieved using a rigorous ISO-17100 certified methodology¹ involving:

- a process which comprises several steps
- the instrument's developer input on conceptual issues
- a skilled team recruited by **ICON Language Services** in the target country and headed by a consultant with knowledge of and experience in the field of Clinical Outcome Assessments. The consultant supervises and coordinates the linguistic validation process in his/her country
- a centralized review process coordinated by **ICON Language Services**, including quality control by linguists and discussions about translation decisions with the consultant at each step of the process.
- cross-cultural harmonisation to ensure common understanding of the instrument's concepts by all participants involved in the process and achieve conceptual equivalence across languages.

The aforementioned translation (filename : German (Germany)_EUonQoL Toolkit V2_10APR2024, dated 10 April 2024) underwent the following steps:

- Forward Translation step – 2 forward translations by qualified translators and reconciliation Backtranslation step
- – 1 backtranslation by a qualified translator
- Cognitive Interview step:
 - 5 participants; population: 2 participants with breast cancer, 1 with ovarian cancer and 2 with lung cancer;
 - group: Adults; age range: 18-80+
- Proofreading step

ICON Language Services may not be held liable for any changes made on the translation after completion of project **6353-TR-0001** by **ICON Language Services** on **10 April 2024**.

Laurine Labbe
Associate PM
ICON Language Services

¹ References

- Acquadro C, Jambon B., Ellis D. and Marquis P. Language and translation issues. In Spilker B, ed. Quality of Life and Pharmacoeconomics in Clinical Trials. Philadelphia: Lippincott-Raven Publishers, 1996: 575-585. - Linguistic Validation Manual for Health Outcomes Assessments. Acquadro C, Conway K, Giroudet C, Mear I. Second Edition - Mapi Institute, Lyon, France, January 2012 - ISBN: 2-9522021-0-9

Laurine Labbe Laurine Labbe
10 Apr 2024 09:09:32 UTC (Z)

REASON: I approve this document

8512aa70 d9ac 1af2 aad7 cb8fb119629c

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2.5.12. Greek Linguistic Validation Certificate

LINGUISTIC VALIDATION CERTIFICATE

EUonQoL v2.0 (EUonQoL v2.0)

This is to certify that **ICON Language Services** conducted the linguistic validation of the Electronic version of the EUonQoL v2.0 (source file name: English (UK)_EUonQoL Toolkit V2.0) into Greece - Greek.

The aim of linguistic validation is to obtain translations that are:

- conceptually equivalent to the original and comparable across languages
- culturally relevant to the context of the target country
- easily understood by the people to whom the translated instrument is administered.

This is achieved using a rigorous ISO-17100 certified methodology¹ involving:

- a process which comprises several steps
- the instrument's developer input on conceptual issues
- a skilled team recruited by **ICON Language Services** in the target country and headed by a consultant with knowledge of and experience in the field of Clinical Outcome Assessments. The consultant supervises and coordinates the linguistic validation process in his/her country
- a centralized review process coordinated by **ICON Language Services**, including quality control by linguists and discussions about translation decisions with the consultant at each step of the process.
- cross-cultural harmonisation to ensure common understanding of the instrument's concepts by all participants involved in the process and achieve conceptual equivalence across languages.

The aforementioned translation (filename : Greek (Greece)_EUonQoL Toolkit V2.0_09APR2024, dated 9 April 2024) underwent the following steps:

- Forward Translation step – 2 forward translations by qualified translators and reconciliation
- Backtranslation step – 1 backtranslation by a qualified translator
- Cognitive Interview step:
 - 5 participants; population: Cancer; group: Adults; age range: 18-80+
- Proofreading step

ICON Language Services may not be held liable for any changes made on the translation after completion of project **6353-TR-0001** by **ICON Language Services** on **9 April 2024**.

Laurine Labbe
Associate PM
ICON Language Services

Laurine Labbe
09 Apr 2024 14:37:40 UTC (Z)

REASON: I approve this document

8512aa70-09ac-1ed2-aaa9-cb88fb114029c

¹ References

- Acquadro C, Jambon B, Ellis D. and Marquis P. Language and translation issues. In Spilker B, ed. Quality of Life and Pharmacoeconomics in Clinical Trials. Philadelphia: Lippincott-Raven Publishers, 1996: 575-585. - Linguistic Validation Manual for Health Outcomes Assessments. Acquadro C, Conway K, Giroudet C, Mear I. Second Edition - Mapi Institute, Lyon, France, January 2012 - ISBN: 2-9522021-0-9

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2.5.13. Hungarian Linguistic Validation Certificate

LINGUISTIC VALIDATION CERTIFICATE

EUonQoL v2.0 (EUonQoL v2.0)

This is to certify that **ICON Language Services** conducted the linguistic validation of the Electronic version of the EUonQoL v2.0 (source file name: English (UK)_EUonQoL Toolkit V2.0) into Hungary - Hungarian.

The aim of linguistic validation is to obtain translations that are:

- conceptually equivalent to the original and comparable across languages
- culturally relevant to the context of the target country
- easily understood by the people to whom the translated instrument is administered.

This is achieved using a rigorous ISO-17100 certified methodology¹ involving:

- a process which comprises several steps
- the instrument's developer input on conceptual issues
- a skilled team recruited by **ICON Language Services** in the target country and headed by a consultant with knowledge of and experience in the field of Clinical Outcome Assessments. The consultant supervises and coordinates the linguistic validation process in his/her country
- a centralized review process coordinated by **ICON Language Services**, including quality control by linguists and discussions about translation decisions with the consultant at each step of the process.
- cross-cultural harmonisation to ensure common understanding of the instrument's concepts by all participants involved in the process and achieve conceptual equivalence across languages.

The aforementioned translation (filename : Hungarian (Hungary)_EUonQoL Toolkit V2.0_09APR2024, dated 9 April 2024) underwent the following steps:

- Forward Translation step – 2 forward translations by qualified translators and reconciliation
- Backtranslation step – 1 backtranslation by a qualified translator
- Cognitive Interview step:
 - 5 participants; population: Cancer; group: Adults
- Proofreading step

ICON Language Services may not be held liable for any changes made on the translation after completion of project **6353-TR-0001** by **ICON Language Services** on **9 April 2024**.

Becki Ellsmore
Associate Project Manager
ICON Language Services

Becki Ellsmore
09 Apr 2024 16:04:34 UTC (Z)
REASON: I approve this document

d79d211b-27af-48ba-963e-ac7acc28f7a

¹ References

- Acquadro C, Jambon B, Ellis D. and Marquis P. Language and translation issues. In Spilker B, ed. Quality of Life and Pharmacoeconomics in Clinical Trials. Philadelphia: Lippincott-Raven Publishers, 1996: 575-585. - Linguistic Validation Manual for Health Outcomes Assessments. Acquadro C, Conway K, Giroudet C, Mear I. Second Edition - Mapi Institute, Lyon, France, January 2012 - ISBN: 2-9522021-0-9

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2.5.14. Italian Linguistic Validation Certificate

LINGUISTIC VALIDATION CERTIFICATE

EUonQoL v2.0 (EUonQoL v2.0)

This is to certify that **ICON Language Services** conducted the linguistic validation of the Electronic version of the EUonQoL v2.0 (source file name: English (UK)_EUonQoL Toolkit V2.0) into Italy - Italian.

The aim of linguistic validation is to obtain translations that are:

- conceptually equivalent to the original and comparable across languages
- culturally relevant to the context of the target country
- easily understood by the people to whom the translated instrument is administered.

This is achieved using a rigorous ISO-17100 certified methodology¹ involving:

- a process which comprises several steps
- the instrument's developer input on conceptual issues
- a skilled team recruited by **ICON Language Services** in the target country and headed by a consultant with knowledge of and experience in the field of Clinical Outcome Assessments. The consultant supervises and coordinates the linguistic validation process in his/her country
- a centralized review process coordinated by **ICON Language Services**, including quality control by linguists and discussions about translation decisions with the consultant at each step of the process.
- cross-cultural harmonisation to ensure common understanding of the instrument's concepts by all participants involved in the process and achieve conceptual equivalence across languages.

The aforementioned translation (filename : Italian (Italy)_EUonQoL Toolkit V2_04APR2024, dated 4 April 2024) underwent the following steps:

- Forward Translation step – 2 forward translations by qualified translators and reconciliation
- Backtranslation step – 1 backtranslation by a qualified translator
- Cognitive Interview step:
 - 5 participants; population: Cancer; group: Adults; age range: 25-70
- Proofreading step

ICON Language Services may not be held liable for any changes made on the translation after completion of project **6353-TR-0001** by **ICON Language Services** on **4 April 2024**.

Jade Mermet-Grossi
Project Manager
ICON Language Services

Jade Mermet-Grossi Jade Mermet-Grossi
04 Apr 2024 13:08:49 UTC (Z)

REASON: I approve this document

c0c0ba66 b955 4b99 ab40 985a26676582

¹ References

- Acquadro C, Jambon B., Ellis D. and Marquis P. Language and translation issues. In Spilker B, ed. Quality of Life and Pharmacoeconomics in Clinical Trials. Philadelphia: Lippincott-Raven Publishers, 1996: 575-585. - Linguistic Validation Manual for Health Outcomes Assessments. Acquadro C, Conway K, Giroudet C, Mear I. Second Edition - Mapi Institute, Lyon, France, January 2012 - ISBN: 2-9522021-0-9

2.5.15. Latvian Linguistic Validation Certificate

LINGUISTIC VALIDATION CERTIFICATE

EUonQoL v2.0 (EUonQoL v2.0)

This is to certify that **ICON Language Services** conducted the linguistic validation of the Electronic version of the EUonQoL v2.0 (source file name: English (UK)_EUonQoL Toolkit V2.0) into Latvia - Latvian.

The aim of linguistic validation is to obtain translations that are:

- conceptually equivalent to the original and comparable across languages
- culturally relevant to the context of the target country
- easily understood by the people to whom the translated instrument is administered.

This is achieved using a rigorous ISO-17100 certified methodology¹ involving:

- a process which comprises several steps
- the instrument's developer input on conceptual issues
- a skilled team recruited by **ICON Language Services** in the target country and headed by a consultant with knowledge of and experience in the field of Clinical Outcome Assessments. The consultant supervises and coordinates the linguistic validation process in his/her country
- a centralized review process coordinated by **ICON Language Services**, including quality control by linguists and discussions about translation decisions with the consultant at each step of the process.
- cross-cultural harmonisation to ensure common understanding of the instrument's concepts by all participants involved in the process and achieve conceptual equivalence across languages.

The aforementioned translation (filename : Latvian (Latvia)_EUonQoL Toolkit V2.0_10APR2024, dated 10 April 2024) underwent the following steps:

- Forward Translation step – 2 forward translations by qualified translators and reconciliation
- Backtranslation step – 1 backtranslation by a qualified translator
- Cognitive Interview step:
 - 5 participants; population: Cancer; group: Adults
- Proofreading step

ICON Language Services may not be held liable for any changes made on the translation after completion of project **6353-TR-0001** by **ICON Language Services** on **10 April 2024**.

Emilie Crespo De Place
Project Manager, PCS
ICON Language Services

Emilie Crespo de Place Emilie Crespo de Place
10 Apr 2024 09:34:48 UTC (Z)
REASON: I approve this document

acb39de3-66a9-4573-8a2c-f1a5e5828df2

¹ References

- Acquadro C., Jambon B., Ellis D. and Marquis P. Language and translation issues. In Spilker B, ed. Quality of Life and Pharmacoeconomics in Clinical Trials. Philadelphia: Lippincott-Raven Publishers, 1996: 575-585. - Linguistic Validation Manual for Health Outcomes Assessments. Acquadro C, Conway K, Giroulet C, Mearl. Second Edition - Mapi Institute, Lyon, France, January 2012 - ISBN: 2-9522021-0-9

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2.5.16. Lithuanian Linguistic Validation Certificate

LINGUISTIC VALIDATION CERTIFICATE

EUonQoL v2.0 (EUonQoL v2.0)

This is to certify that **ICON Language Services** conducted the linguistic validation of the Electronic version of the EUonQoL v2.0 (source file name: English (UK)_EUonQoL Toolkit V2.0) into Lithuania - Lithuanian.

The aim of linguistic validation is to obtain translations that are:

- conceptually equivalent to the original and comparable across languages
- culturally relevant to the context of the target country
- easily understood by the people to whom the translated instrument is administered.

This is achieved using a rigorous ISO-17100 certified methodology¹ involving:

- a process which comprises several steps
- the instrument's developer input on conceptual issues
- a skilled team recruited by **ICON Language Services** in the target country and headed by a consultant with knowledge of and experience in the field of Clinical Outcome Assessments. The consultant supervises and coordinates the linguistic validation process in his/her country
- a centralized review process coordinated by **ICON Language Services**, including quality control by linguists and discussions about translation decisions with the consultant at each step of the process.
- cross-cultural harmonisation to ensure common understanding of the instrument's concepts by all participants involved in the process and achieve conceptual equivalence across languages.

The aforementioned translation (filename : Lithuanian (Lithuania)_EUonQoL Toolkit V2.0_09APR2024, dated 9 April 2024) underwent the following steps:

- Forward Translation step – 2 forward translations by qualified translators and reconciliation
- Backtranslation step – 1 backtranslation by a qualified translator
- Cognitive Interview step:
 - 5 participants; population: Cancer; group: Adults
- Proofreading step

ICON Language Services may not be held liable for any changes made on the translation after completion of project **6353-TR-0001** by **ICON Language Services** on **9 April 2024**.

Emilie Crespo De Place
Project Manager, PCS
ICON Language Services

Emilie Crespo de Place Emilie Crespo de Place
09 Apr 2024 15:22:10 UTC (Z)

REASON: I approve this document

act39ac3 66a9 4573 8a2c f1a5e5828e82

¹ References

- Acquadro C, Jambon B, Ellis D. and Marquis P. Language and translation issues. In Spilker B, ed. Quality of Life and Pharmacoeconomics in Clinical Trials. Philadelphia: Lippincott-Raven Publishers, 1996: 575-585. - Linguistic Validation Manual for Health Outcomes Assessments. Acquadro C, Conway K, Giroudet C, Mear I. Second Edition - Mapi Institute, Lyon, France, January 2012 - ISBN: 2-9522021-0-9

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2.5.17. Maltese Linguistic Validation Certificate

LINGUISTIC VALIDATION CERTIFICATE

EUonQoL v2.0 (EUonQoL v2.0)

This is to certify that **ICON Language Services** conducted the linguistic validation of the Electronic version of the EUonQoL v2.0 (source file name: English (UK)_EUonQoL Toolkit V2.0) into Malta - Maltese.

The aim of linguistic validation is to obtain translations that are:

- conceptually equivalent to the original and comparable across languages
- culturally relevant to the context of the target country
- easily understood by the people to whom the translated instrument is administered.

This is achieved using a rigorous ISO-17100 certified methodology¹ involving:

- a process which comprises several steps
- the instrument's developer input on conceptual issues
- a skilled team recruited by **ICON Language Services** in the target country and headed by a consultant with knowledge of and experience in the field of Clinical Outcome Assessments. The consultant supervises and coordinates the linguistic validation process in his/her country
- a centralized review process coordinated by **ICON Language Services**, including quality control by linguists and discussions about translation decisions with the consultant at each step of the process.
- cross-cultural harmonisation to ensure common understanding of the instrument's concepts by all participants involved in the process and achieve conceptual equivalence across languages.

The aforementioned translation (filename : Maltese (Malta)_EUonQoL Toolkit V2.0_10APR2024, dated 10 April 2024) underwent the following steps:

- Forward Translation step – 2 forward translations by qualified translators and reconciliation
- Backtranslation step – 1 backtranslation by a qualified translator
- Cognitive Interview step:
 - 5 participants; population: Cancer; group: Adults
- Proofreading step

ICON Language Services may not be held liable for any changes made on the translation after completion of project **6353-TR-0001** by **ICON Language Services** on **10 April 2024**.

Adrien Bonnier
Project Manager
ICON Language Services

Adrien Bonnier Adrien Bonnier
10 Apr 2024 08:58:21 UTC (Z)

REASON: I approve this document

78b606d 7c20 4995 ab86 3c0a3b24326d

¹ References

- Acquadro C, Jambon B., Ellis D. and Marquis P. Language and translation issues. In Spilker B, ed. Quality of Life and Pharmacoeconomics in Clinical Trials. Philadelphia: Lippincott-Raven Publishers, 1996: 575-585. - Linguistic Validation Manual for Health Outcomes Assessments. Acquadro C, Conway K, Giroudet C, Mear I. Second Edition - Mapi Institute, Lyon, France, January 2012 - ISBN: 2-9522021-0-9

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2.5.18. Moldovan Linguistic Validation Certificate

LINGUISTIC VALIDATION CERTIFICATE

EUonQoL v2.0 (EUonQoL v2.0)

This is to certify that **ICON Language Services** conducted the linguistic validation of the Electronic version of the EUonQoL v2.0 (source file name: English (UK)_EUonQoL Toolkit V2.0) into Moldova - Romanian.

The aim of linguistic validation is to obtain translations that are:

- conceptually equivalent to the original and comparable across languages
- culturally relevant to the context of the target country
- easily understood by the people to whom the translated instrument is administered.

This is achieved using a rigorous ISO-17100 certified methodology¹ involving:

- a process which comprises several steps
- the instrument's developer input on conceptual issues
- a skilled team recruited by **ICON Language Services** in the target country and headed by a consultant with knowledge of and experience in the field of Clinical Outcome Assessments. The consultant supervises and coordinates the linguistic validation process in his/her country
- a centralized review process coordinated by **ICON Language Services**, including quality control by linguists and discussions about translation decisions with the consultant at each step of the process.
- cross-cultural harmonisation to ensure common understanding of the instrument's concepts by all participants involved in the process and achieve conceptual equivalence across languages.

The aforementioned translation (filename : Romanian (Moldova)_EUonQoL Toolkit V2.0_05APR2024, dated 5 April 2024) underwent the following steps:

- Adaptation step based on the Romanian version for Romania in order to render the translation appropriate for the context of Moldova
- Cognitive Interview step:
 - 5 participants; population: Cancer; group: Adults; age range: 18-80+
- Proofreading step

The mother version on which the linguistic validation work was based had previously undergone the following steps:

- Forward Translation
- Back Translation

ICON Language Services may not be held liable for any changes made on the translation after completion of project **6353-TR-0001** by **ICON Language Services** on **5 April 2024**.

Veronica Gonzalez De La Rosa
Project Manager
ICON Language Services

Veronica Gonzalez de la Rosa Veronica Gonzalez de la Rosa
05 Apr 2024 07:55:38 UTC (Z)
REASON: I approve this document
d99b36af 2af6 4382 9acd 6457219b2899

¹ References

- Acquadro C, Jambon B., Ellis D. and Marquis P. Language and translation issues. In Spilker B, ed. Quality of Life and Pharmacoeconomics in Clinical Trials. Philadelphia: Lippincott-Raven Publishers, 1996: 575-585. - Linguistic Validation Manual for Health Outcomes Assessments. Acquadro C, Conway K, Giroudet C, Mear I. Second Edition - Mapi Institute, Lyon, France, January 2012 - ISBN: 2-9522021-0-9

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2.5.19. Norwegian Linguistic Validation Certificate

LINGUISTIC VALIDATION CERTIFICATE

EUonQoL v2.0 (EUonQoL v2.0)

This is to certify that **ICON Language Services** conducted the linguistic validation of the Electronic version of the EUonQoL v2.0 (source file name: English (UK)_EUonQoL Toolkit V2.0) into Norway - Norwegian.

The aim of linguistic validation is to obtain translations that are:

- conceptually equivalent to the original and comparable across languages
- culturally relevant to the context of the target country
- easily understood by the people to whom the translated instrument is administered.

This is achieved using a rigorous ISO-17100 certified methodology¹ involving:

- a process which comprises several steps
- the instrument's developer input on conceptual issues
- a skilled team recruited by **ICON Language Services** in the target country and headed by a consultant with knowledge of and experience in the field of Clinical Outcome Assessments. The consultant supervises and coordinates the linguistic validation process in his/her country
- a centralized review process coordinated by **ICON Language Services**, including quality control by linguists and discussions about translation decisions with the consultant at each step of the process.
- cross-cultural harmonisation to ensure common understanding of the instrument's concepts by all participants involved in the process and achieve conceptual equivalence across languages.

The aforementioned translation (filename : Norwegian (Norway)_EUonQoL Toolkit V2.0_04APR2024, dated 4 April 2024) underwent the following steps:

- Forward Translation step – 2 forward translations by qualified translators and reconciliation
- Backtranslation step – 1 backtranslation by a qualified translator
- Cognitive Interview step:
 - 5 participants; population: Cancer; group: Adults
- Proofreading step

ICON Language Services may not be held liable for any changes made on the translation after completion of project **6353-TR-0001** by **ICON Language Services** on **4 April 2024**.

Adrien Bonnier
Project Manager
ICON Language Services

Adrien Bonnier Adrien Bonnier
04 Apr 2024 10:51:08 UTC (Z)

REASON: I approve this document

78b9b06d 7c20 4195 ab86 3eda3ba21326d

¹ References

- Acquadro C, Jambon B., Ellis D. and Marquis P. Language and translation issues. In Spilker B, ed. Quality of Life and Pharmacoeconomics in Clinical Trials. Philadelphia: Lippincott-Raven Publishers, 1996: 575-585. - Linguistic Validation Manual for Health Outcomes Assessments. Acquadro C, Conway K, Giroudet C, Mear I. Second Edition - Mapi Institute, Lyon, France, January 2012 - ISBN: 2-9522021-0-9

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2.5.20. Polish Linguistic Validation Certificate

LINGUISTIC VALIDATION CERTIFICATE

EUonQoL v2.0 (EUonQoL v2.0)

This is to certify that **ICON Language Services** conducted the linguistic validation of the Electronic version of the EUonQoL v2.0 (source file name: English (UK)_EUonQoL Toolkit V2.0) into Poland - Polish.

The aim of linguistic validation is to obtain translations that are:

- conceptually equivalent to the original and comparable across languages
- culturally relevant to the context of the target country
- easily understood by the people to whom the translated instrument is administered.

This is achieved using a rigorous ISO-17100 certified methodology¹ involving:

- a process which comprises several steps
- the instrument's developer input on conceptual issues
- a skilled team recruited by **ICON Language Services** in the target country and headed by a consultant with knowledge of and experience in the field of Clinical Outcome Assessments. The consultant supervises and coordinates the linguistic validation process in his/her country
- a centralized review process coordinated by **ICON Language Services**, including quality control by linguists and discussions about translation decisions with the consultant at each step of the process.
- cross-cultural harmonisation to ensure common understanding of the instrument's concepts by all participants involved in the process and achieve conceptual equivalence across languages.

The aforementioned translation (filename : Polish (Poland)_EUonQoL Toolkit V2.0_08APR2024, dated 8 April 2024) underwent the following steps:

- Forward Translation step – 2 forward translations by qualified translators and reconciliation
- Backtranslation step – 1 backtranslation by a qualified translator
- Cognitive Interview step:
 - 5 participants; population: Cancer; group: Adults; age range: 31-80
- Proofreading step

ICON Language Services may not be held liable for any changes made on the translation after completion of project **6353-TR-0001** by **ICON Language Services** on **8 April 2024**.

Caroline Price
Associate project manager
ICON Language Services

Caroline Price Caroline Price
08 Apr 2024 14:12:16 UTC (Z)

REASON: I approve this document

28b32e82 c148 4c3e 990d eb17269ca13f

¹ References

- Acquadro C, Jambon B, Ellis D and Marquis P. Language and translation issues. In Spilker B, ed. Quality of Life and Pharmacoeconomics in Clinical Trials. Philadelphia: Lippincott-Raven Publishers, 1996: 575-585. - Linguistic Validation Manual for Health Outcomes Assessments. Acquadro C, Conway K, Giroudet C, Mear I. Second Edition - Mapi Institute, Lyon, France, January 2012 - ISBN: 2-9522021-0-9

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2.5.21. Portuguese Linguistic Validation Certificate

LINGUISTIC VALIDATION CERTIFICATE

EUonQoL v2.0 (EUonQoL v2.0)

This is to certify that **ICON Language Services** conducted the linguistic validation of the Electronic version of the EUonQoL v2.0 (source file name: English (UK)_EUonQoL Toolkit V2.0) into Portugal - Portuguese.

The aim of linguistic validation is to obtain translations that are:

- conceptually equivalent to the original and comparable across languages
- culturally relevant to the context of the target country
- easily understood by the people to whom the translated instrument is administered.

This is achieved using a rigorous ISO-17100 certified methodology¹ involving:

- a process which comprises several steps
- the instrument's developer input on conceptual issues
- a skilled team recruited by **ICON Language Services** in the target country and headed by a consultant with knowledge of and experience in the field of Clinical Outcome Assessments. The consultant supervises and coordinates the linguistic validation process in his/her country
- a centralized review process coordinated by **ICON Language Services**, including quality control by linguists and discussions about translation decisions with the consultant at each step of the process.
- cross-cultural harmonisation to ensure common understanding of the instrument's concepts by all participants involved in the process and achieve conceptual equivalence across languages.

The aforementioned translation (filename : Portuguese (Portugal)_EUonQoL Toolkit V2.0_25MAR2024, dated 25 March 2024) underwent the following steps:

- Forward Translation step – 2 forward translations by qualified translators and reconciliation
- Backtranslation step – 1 backtranslation by a qualified translator
- Cognitive Interview step:
 - 5 participants; population: Cancer
- Proofreading step

ICON Language Services may not be held liable for any changes made on the translation after completion of project **6353-TR-0001** by **ICON Language Services** on **25 March 2024**.

Alexia Dos Santos Campanha
Project Manager
ICON Language Services

Alexia Dos Santos Campanha Alexia Dos Santos Campanha
25 Mar 2024 14:17:53 UTC (Z)
REASON: I approve this document
Ba30aac7 6756 4032 bc19 9c9c7431963f

¹ References

- Acquadro C, Jambon B, Ellis D. and Marquis P. Language and translation issues. In Spilker B, ed. Quality of Life and Pharmacoeconomics in Clinical Trials. Philadelphia: Lippincott-Raven Publishers, 1996: 575-585. - Linguistic Validation Manual for Health Outcomes Assessments. Acquadro C, Conway K, Giroudet C, Mear I. Second Edition - Mapi Institute, Lyon, France, January 2012 - ISBN: 2-9522021-0-9

<p style="text-align: center;">Funded by the European Union</p>		
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2.5.22. Romanian Linguistic Validation Certificate

LINGUISTIC VALIDATION CERTIFICATE

EUonQoL v2.0 (EUonQoL v2.0)

This is to certify that **ICON Language Services** conducted the linguistic validation of the Electronic version of the EUonQoL v2.0 (source file name: English (UK)_EUonQoL Toolkit V2.0) into Romania - Romanian.

The aim of linguistic validation is to obtain translations that are:

- conceptually equivalent to the original and comparable across languages
- culturally relevant to the context of the target country
- easily understood by the people to whom the translated instrument is administered.

This is achieved using a rigorous ISO-17100 certified methodology¹ involving:

- a process which comprises several steps
- the instrument's developer input on conceptual issues
- a skilled team recruited by **ICON Language Services** in the target country and headed by a consultant with knowledge of and experience in the field of Clinical Outcome Assessments. The consultant supervises and coordinates the linguistic validation process in his/her country
- a centralized review process coordinated by **ICON Language Services**, including quality control by linguists and discussions about translation decisions with the consultant at each step of the process.
- cross-cultural harmonisation to ensure common understanding of the instrument's concepts by all participants involved in the process and achieve conceptual equivalence across languages.

The aforementioned translation (filename : Romanian (Romania)_EUonQoL Toolkit V2_04APR2024, dated 4 April 2024) underwent the following steps:

- Forward Translation step – 2 forward translations by qualified translators and reconciliation
- Backtranslation step – 1 backtranslation by a qualified translator
- Cognitive Interview step:
 - 5 participants; population: Cancer; group: Adults; age range: 25-80
- Proofreading step

ICON Language Services may not be held liable for any changes made on the translation after completion of project **6353-TR-0001** by **ICON Language Services** on **4 April 2024**.

Jade Mermet-Grossi
Project Manager
ICON Language Services

Jade Mermet-Grossi Jade Mermet-Grossi
04 Apr 2024 13:08:50 UTC (Z)

REASON: I approve this document

c0c0ba6 bf35 1b79 abfd 981a26670382

¹ References

- Acquadro C, Jambon B, Ellis D. and Marquis P. Language and translation issues. In Spilker B, ed. Quality of Life and Pharmacoeconomics in Clinical Trials. Philadelphia: Lippincott-Raven Publishers, 1996: 575-585. - Linguistic Validation Manual for Health Outcomes Assessments. Acquadro C, Conway K, Giroudet C, Mear I. Second Edition - Mapi Institute, Lyon, France, January 2012 - ISBN: 2-9522021-0-9

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2.5.23. Serbian Linguistic Validation Certificate

LINGUISTIC VALIDATION CERTIFICATE

EUonQoL v2.0 (EUonQoL v2.0)

This is to certify that **ICON Language Services** conducted the linguistic validation of the Electronic version of the EUonQoL v2.0 (source file name: English (UK)_EUonQoL Toolkit V2.0) into Serbia - Serbian - Latin.

The aim of linguistic validation is to obtain translations that are:

- conceptually equivalent to the original and comparable across languages
- culturally relevant to the context of the target country
- easily understood by the people to whom the translated instrument is administered.

This is achieved using a rigorous ISO-17100 certified methodology¹ involving:

- a process which comprises several steps
- the instrument's developer input on conceptual issues
- a skilled team recruited by **ICON Language Services** in the target country and headed by a consultant with knowledge of and experience in the field of Clinical Outcome Assessments. The consultant supervises and coordinates the linguistic validation process in his/her country
- a centralized review process coordinated by **ICON Language Services**, including quality control by linguists and discussions about translation decisions with the consultant at each step of the process.
- cross-cultural harmonisation to ensure common understanding of the instrument's concepts by all participants involved in the process and achieve conceptual equivalence across languages.

The aforementioned translation (filename : Serbian (Serbia)_EUonQoL Toolkit V2.0_09APR2024, dated 9 April 2024) underwent the following steps:

- Forward Translation step – 2 forward translations by qualified translators and reconciliation
- Backtranslation step – 1 backtranslation by a qualified translator
- Cognitive Interview step:
 - 5 participants; population: Cancer; group: Adults; age range: 41-80
- Proofreading step

ICON Language Services may not be held liable for any changes made on the translation after completion of project **6353-TR-0001** by **ICON Language Services** on **9 April 2024**.

Caroline Price
Associate project manager
ICON Language Services

Caroline Price Caroline Price
09 Apr 2024 14:49:30 UTC (Z)

REASON: I approve this document

286d2e82 c148 4c3e 990d eb17207c912f

¹ References

- Acquadro C, Jambon B, Ellis D. and Marquis P. Language and translation issues. In Spilker B, ed. Quality of Life and Pharmacoeconomics in Clinical Trials. Philadelphia: Lippincott-Raven Publishers, 1996: 575-585. - Linguistic Validation Manual for Health Outcomes Assessments. Acquadro C, Conway K, Giroudet C, Mear I. Second Edition - Mapi Institute, Lyon, France, January 2012 - ISBN: 2-9522021-0-9

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2.5.24. Slovak Linguistic Validation Certificate

LINGUISTIC VALIDATION CERTIFICATE

EUonQoL v2.0 (EUonQoL v2.0)

This is to certify that **ICON Language Services** conducted the linguistic validation of the Electronic version of the EUonQoL v2.0 (source file name: English (UK)_EUonQoL Toolkit V2.0) into Slovakia - Slovak.

The aim of linguistic validation is to obtain translations that are:

- conceptually equivalent to the original and comparable across languages
- culturally relevant to the context of the target country
- easily understood by the people to whom the translated instrument is administered.

This is achieved using a rigorous ISO-17100 certified methodology¹ involving:

- a process which comprises several steps
- the instrument's developer input on conceptual issues
- a skilled team recruited by **ICON Language Services** in the target country and headed by a consultant with knowledge of and experience in the field of Clinical Outcome Assessments. The consultant supervises and coordinates the linguistic validation process in his/her country
- a centralized review process coordinated by **ICON Language Services**, including quality control by linguists and discussions about translation decisions with the consultant at each step of the process.
- cross-cultural harmonisation to ensure common understanding of the instrument's concepts by all participants involved in the process and achieve conceptual equivalence across languages.

The aforementioned translation (filename : Slovak (Slovakia)_EUonQoL Toolkit V2.0_09APR2024, dated 9 April 2024) underwent the following steps:

- Forward Translation step – 2 forward translations by qualified translators and reconciliation
- Backtranslation step – 1 backtranslation by a qualified translator
- Cognitive Interview step:
 - 5 participants; population: Cancer; group: Adults; age range: 25-60
- Proofreading step

ICON Language Services may not be held liable for any changes made on the translation after completion of project **6353-TR-0001** by **ICON Language Services** on **9 April 2024**.

Rocio Lorenzo Lopez
Project Manager
ICON Language Services

Rocio Lorenzo Lopez
09 Apr 2024 10:49:48 UTC (Z)
REASON: I approve this document
a30c0a82 6bc9 45a0 9953 8d90aad92a17

¹ References

- Acquadro C, Jambon B, Ellis D and Marquis P. Language and translation issues. In Spilker B, ed. Quality of Life and Pharmacoeconomics in Clinical Trials. Philadelphia: Lippincott-Raven Publishers, 1996: 575-585. - Linguistic Validation Manual for Health Outcomes Assessments. Acquadro C, Conway K, Giroudet C, Mear I. Second Edition - Mapi Institute, Lyon, France, January 2012 - ISBN: 2-9522021-0-9

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2.5.25. Slovenian Linguistic Validation Certificate

LINGUISTIC VALIDATION CERTIFICATE

EUonQoL v2.0 (EUonQoL v2.0)

This is to certify that **ICON Language Services** conducted the linguistic validation of the Electronic version of the EUonQoL v2.0 (source file name: English (UK)_EUonQoL Toolkit V2.0) into Slovenia - Slovenian.

The aim of linguistic validation is to obtain translations that are:

- conceptually equivalent to the original and comparable across languages
- culturally relevant to the context of the target country
- easily understood by the people to whom the translated instrument is administered.

This is achieved using a rigorous ISO-17100 certified methodology¹ involving:

- a process which comprises several steps
- the instrument's developer input on conceptual issues
- a skilled team recruited by **ICON Language Services** in the target country and headed by a consultant with knowledge of and experience in the field of Clinical Outcome Assessments. The consultant supervises and coordinates the linguistic validation process in his/her country
- a centralized review process coordinated by **ICON Language Services**, including quality control by linguists and discussions about translation decisions with the consultant at each step of the process.
- cross-cultural harmonisation to ensure common understanding of the instrument's concepts by all participants involved in the process and achieve conceptual equivalence across languages.

The aforementioned translation (filename : Slovenian (Slovenia)_EUonQoL Toolkit V2.0_08APR2024, dated 8 April 2024) underwent the following steps:

- Forward Translation step – 2 forward translations by qualified translators and reconciliation
- Backtranslation step – 1 backtranslation by a qualified translator
- Cognitive Interview step:
 - 5 participants; population: Cancer; group: Adults; age range: 31-70
- Proofreading step

ICON Language Services may not be held liable for any changes made on the translation after completion of project **6353-TR-0001** by **ICON Language Services** on **8 April 2024**.

Rocio Lorenzo Lopez
Project Manager
ICON Language Services

Rocio Lorenzo Lopez Rocio Lorenzo Lopez
08 Apr 2024 08:05:02 UTC (Z)
REASON: I approve this document
a30c0a82-6bc9-45a0-9553-8d90aad92a17

¹ References

- Acquadro C, Jambon B, Ellis D. and Marquis P. Language and translation issues. In Spilker B, ed. Quality of Life and Pharmacoeconomics in Clinical Trials. Philadelphia: Lippincott-Raven Publishers, 1996: 575-585. - Linguistic Validation Manual for Health Outcomes Assessments. Acquadro C, Conway K, Giroudet C, Mear I. Second Edition - Mapi Institute, Lyon, France, January 2012 - ISBN: 2-9522021-0-9

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2.5.26. Spanish Linguistic Validation Certificate

LINGUISTIC VALIDATION CERTIFICATE

EUonQoL v2.0 (EUonQoL v2.0)

This is to certify that **ICON Language Services** conducted the linguistic validation of the Electronic version of the EUonQoL v2.0 (source file name: English (UK)_EUonQoL Toolkit V2.0) into Spain - Spanish (European).

The aim of linguistic validation is to obtain translations that are:

- conceptually equivalent to the original and comparable across languages
- culturally relevant to the context of the target country
- easily understood by the people to whom the translated instrument is administered.

This is achieved using a rigorous ISO-17100 certified methodology¹ involving:

- a process which comprises several steps
- the instrument's developer input on conceptual issues
- a skilled team recruited by **ICON Language Services** in the target country and headed by a consultant with knowledge of and experience in the field of Clinical Outcome Assessments. The consultant supervises and coordinates the linguistic validation process in his/her country
- a centralized review process coordinated by **ICON Language Services**, including quality control by linguists and discussions about translation decisions with the consultant at each step of the process.
- cross-cultural harmonisation to ensure common understanding of the instrument's concepts by all participants involved in the process and achieve conceptual equivalence across languages.

The aforementioned translation (filename : Spanish (Spain)_EUonQoL Toolkit V2.0_03APR2024, dated 3 April 2024) underwent the following steps:

- Forward Translation step – 2 forward translations by qualified translators and reconciliation
- Backtranslation step – 1 backtranslation by a qualified translator
- Cognitive Interview step:
 - 5 participants; population: Cancer; group: Adults; age range: 18-80+
- Proofreading step

ICON Language Services may not be held liable for any changes made on the translation after completion of project **6353-TR-0001** by **ICON Language Services** on **3 April 2024**.

Veronica Gonzalez De La Rosa
Project Manager
ICON Language Services

Veronica Gonzalez de la Rosa Veronica Gonzalez de la Rosa
04 Apr 2024 15:13:13 UTC (Z)

REASON: I approve this document

010b16af 2af6 4282 fced 6137219b6289

¹ References

- Acquadro C, Jambon B, Ellis D. and Marquis P. Language and translation issues. In Spilker B, ed. Quality of Life and Pharmacoeconomics in Clinical Trials. Philadelphia: Lippincott-Raven Publishers, 1996: 575-585. - Linguistic Validation Manual for Health Outcomes Assessments. Acquadro C, Conway K, Giroudet C, Mear I. Second Edition - Mapi Institute, Lyon, France, January 2012 - ISBN: 2-9522021-0-9

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2.5.27. Swedish Linguistic Validation Certificate

LINGUISTIC VALIDATION CERTIFICATE

EUonQoL v2.0 (EUonQoL v2.0)

This is to certify that **ICON Language Services** conducted the linguistic validation of the Electronic version of the EUonQoL v2.0 (source file name: English (UK)_EUonQoL Toolkit V2.0) into Sweden - Swedish.

The aim of linguistic validation is to obtain translations that are:

- conceptually equivalent to the original and comparable across languages
- culturally relevant to the context of the target country
- easily understood by the people to whom the translated instrument is administered.

This is achieved using a rigorous ISO-17100 certified methodology¹ involving:

- a process which comprises several steps
- the instrument's developer input on conceptual issues
- a skilled team recruited by **ICON Language Services** in the target country and headed by a consultant with knowledge of and experience in the field of Clinical Outcome Assessments. The consultant supervises and coordinates the linguistic validation process in his/her country
- a centralized review process coordinated by **ICON Language Services**, including quality control by linguists and discussions about translation decisions with the consultant at each step of the process.
- cross-cultural harmonisation to ensure common understanding of the instrument's concepts by all participants involved in the process and achieve conceptual equivalence across languages.

The aforementioned translation (filename : Swedish (Sweden)_EUonQoL Toolkit V2.0_05APR2024, dated 5 April 2024) underwent the following steps:

- Forward Translation step – 2 forward translations by qualified translators and reconciliation
- Backtranslation step – 1 backtranslation by a qualified translator
- Cognitive Interview step:
 - 5 participants; population: Cancer; group: Adults; age range: 18-80+
- Proofreading step

ICON Language Services may not be held liable for any changes made on the translation after completion of project **6353-TR-0001** by **ICON Language Services** on **5 April 2024**.

Veronica Gonzalez De La Rosa
Project Manager
ICON Language Services

Veronica Gonzalez de la Rosa Veronica Gonzalez de la Rosa
05 Apr 2024 07:55:36 UTC (Z)
REASON: I approve this document
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¹ References

- Acquadro C, Jambon B., Ellis D. and Marquis P. Language and translation issues. In Spilker B, ed. Quality of Life and Pharmacoeconomics in Clinical Trials. Philadelphia: Lippincott-Raven Publishers, 1996: 575-585. - Linguistic Validation Manual for Health Outcomes Assessments. Acquadro C, Conway K, Giroudet C, Mear I. Second Edition - Mapi Institute, Lyon, France, January 2012 - ISBN: 2-9522021-0-9

<p style="text-align: center;">Funded by the European Union</p>		
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2.5.28. Turkish Linguistic Validation Certificate

LINGUISTIC VALIDATION CERTIFICATE

EUonQoL v2.0 (EUonQoL v2.0)

This is to certify that **ICON Language Services** conducted the linguistic validation of the Electronic version of the EUonQoL v2.0 (source file name: English (UK)_EUonQoL Toolkit V2.0) into Turkey - Turkish.

The aim of linguistic validation is to obtain translations that are:

- conceptually equivalent to the original and comparable across languages
- culturally relevant to the context of the target country
- easily understood by the people to whom the translated instrument is administered.

This is achieved using a rigorous ISO-17100 certified methodology¹ involving:

- a process which comprises several steps
- the instrument's developer input on conceptual issues
- a skilled team recruited by **ICON Language Services** in the target country and headed by a consultant with knowledge of and experience in the field of Clinical Outcome Assessments. The consultant supervises and coordinates the linguistic validation process in his/her country
- a centralized review process coordinated by **ICON Language Services**, including quality control by linguists and discussions about translation decisions with the consultant at each step of the process.
- cross-cultural harmonisation to ensure common understanding of the instrument's concepts by all participants involved in the process and achieve conceptual equivalence across languages.

The aforementioned translation (filename : Turkish (Turkey)_EUonQoL Toolkit V2_09APR2024, dated 9 April 2024) underwent the following steps:

- Forward Translation step – 2 forward translations by qualified translators and reconciliation
- Backtranslation step – 1 backtranslation by a qualified translator
- Cognitive Interview step:
 - 5 participants; population: Cancer; group: Adults; age range: 18-80+
- Proofreading step

ICON Language Services may not be held liable for any changes made on the translation after completion of project **6353-TR-0001** by **ICON Language Services** on **9 April 2024**.

Sébastien Le Dannois
Project Manager
ICON Language Services

 Sébastien Le Dannois
 09 Apr 2024 09:47:13 UTC (Z)
 REASON: I approve this document
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¹ References

- Acquadro C, Jambon B, Ellis D and Marquis P. Language and translation issues. In Spilker B, ed. Quality of Life and Pharmacoeconomics in Clinical Trials. Philadelphia: Lippincott-Raven Publishers, 1996: 575-585. - Linguistic Validation Manual for Health Outcomes Assessments. Acquadro C, Conway K, Giroudet C, Mear I. Second Edition - Mapi Institute, Lyon, France, January 2012 - ISBN: 2-9522021-0-9

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2.5.29. Ukrainian Linguistic Validation Certificate

LINGUISTIC VALIDATION CERTIFICATE

EUonQoL v2.0 (EUonQoL v2.0)

This is to certify that **ICON Language Services** conducted the linguistic validation of the Electronic version of the EUonQoL v2.0 (source file name: English (UK)_EUonQoL Toolkit V2.0) into Ukraine - Ukrainian.

The aim of linguistic validation is to obtain translations that are:

- conceptually equivalent to the original and comparable across languages
- culturally relevant to the context of the target country
- easily understood by the people to whom the translated instrument is administered.

This is achieved using a rigorous ISO-17100 certified methodology¹ involving:

- a process which comprises several steps
- the instrument's developer input on conceptual issues
- a skilled team recruited by **ICON Language Services** in the target country and headed by a consultant with knowledge of and experience in the field of Clinical Outcome Assessments. The consultant supervises and coordinates the linguistic validation process in his/her country
- a centralized review process coordinated by **ICON Language Services**, including quality control by linguists and discussions about translation decisions with the consultant at each step of the process.
- cross-cultural harmonisation to ensure common understanding of the instrument's concepts by all participants involved in the process and achieve conceptual equivalence across languages.

The aforementioned translation (filename : Ukrainain (Ukraine)_EUonQoL Toolkit V2.0_09APR2024, dated 9 April 2024) underwent the following steps:

- Forward Translation step – 2 forward translations by qualified translators and reconciliation
- Backtranslation step – 1 backtranslation by a qualified translator
- Cognitive Interview step:
 - 5 participants; population: Cancer; group: Adults; age range: 41-70
- Proofreading step

ICON Language Services may not be held liable for any changes made on the translation after completion of project **6353-TR-0001** by **ICON Language Services** on **9 April 2024**.

Clemence Gallud
Project Coordinator
ICON Language Services

¹ References

- Acquadro C, Jambon B, Ellis D. and Marquis P. Language and translation issues. In Spilker B, ed. Quality of Life and Pharmacoeconomics in Clinical Trials. Philadelphia: Lippincott-Raven Publishers, 1996: 575-585. - Linguistic Validation Manual for Health Outcomes Assessments. Acquadro C, Conway K, Giroudet C, Mear I. Second Edition - Mapi Institute, Lyon, France, January 2012 - ISBN: 2-9522021-0-9

Clemence Gallud Clemence Gallud
09 Apr 2024 12:25:55 UTC (Z)

REASON: I approve this document

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<p style="text-align: center;">Funded by the European Union</p>		
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3. Conclusions

Based on the aspects outlined in the provided document, the following conclusions can be drawn. **Successful Completion of Translation and Cultural Adaptation (TCA) Process**; the TCA of the EUonQoL-Kit has been accomplished for all the items included in the kit, adhering to ISPOR guidelines and the Principles of Good Practice (PGP) developed by the TCA Group. The IEO team played a significant role in ensuring the high quality and consistency of the translated questionnaires. Indeed, the translation process followed a meticulous eight-step procedure, including forward translation, reconciliation, backward translation, harmonization, cognitive debriefing, review, proofreading, and the generation of an overall final report.

Noteworthy the use of extensive **item library** containing validated translations from the EORTC-QOL Group facilitated the translation process and minimized duplication efforts, specifically during the **conceptualization** phase. Certain items underwent modification during the TCA process to enhance clarity and cultural relevance. Feedback from **cognitive debriefing** sessions informed adjustments to ensure understandability and appropriateness across different target languages and cultural contexts. The entire translation process involved continuous review and refinement, with feedback from Cognitive Debriefing sessions; this iterative approach aimed to enhance the accuracy in the translations' process. During this phase, challenges such as overlapping translations and conceptual nuances culturally determined, were addressed through collaborative decision-making processes involving translation agencies, the IEO team, and the EORTC Group. Resolution strategies included reassessment of translations, conceptualization refinement, and adaptation for clarity and cultural appropriateness.

In conclusion, the TCA process for the EUonQoL-Kit showed a systematic and collaborative approach to ensure the linguistic validity, cultural relevance, and overall quality of translated questionnaires, facilitating the successful implementation of multicentered surveys and promoting cross-cultural comparability in outcomes research.

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4. Appendix/Table

4.1. Preliminary translations

4.1.1. English-Dutch

Items - English	Dutch
<u>We are interested in some things about you and your health. Please answer all of the questions yourself by SELECTING the number that best applies to you. There are no "right" or "wrong" answers.</u>	<u>Wij zijn geïnteresseerd in bepaalde dingen over u en uw gezondheid. Wilt u alle vragen beantwoorden door het getal te selecteren dat het meest op u van toepassing is? Er zijn geen "juiste" of "onjuiste" antwoorden</u>
Do you have any trouble doing strenuous activities, like carrying a heavy shopping bag or a suitcase?	Heeft u moeite met het doen van inspannende activiteiten zoals het dragen van een zware boodschappentas of een koffer?
Do you have any trouble taking a long walk?	Heeft u moeite met het maken van een lange wandeling?
Do you need help caring for your feet (e.g. cutting your toenails)?	Heeft u hulp nodig bij de verzorging van uw voeten (bv. uw teennagels knippen)?
Do you have any trouble carrying a heavy bag upstairs?	Heeft u moeite om een zware tas de trap op te dragen?
Do you have any trouble taking a long walk carrying a heavy pack on your back (e.g. a filled rucksack)?	Heeft u moeite om een lange wandeling te maken met een zware tas op uw rug (bv. een volle rugzak)?
Do you have any trouble taking a short walk outside of the house?	Heeft u moeite met het maken van een korte wandeling buitenshuis?
Do you need help undressing?	Heeft u hulp nodig bij het uitkleden?
Do you have any trouble walking for 30 min.?	Heeft u moeite om 30 minuten te wandelen?
<u>During the past week:</u>	<u>Gedurende de afgelopen week:</u>
Have you been limited in doing light housework (e.g. dusting or making the bed)?	Was u beperkt in het uitvoeren van lichte huishoudelijke taken (bv. stof afnemen of het bed opmaken)?
Have you been limited in doing physically demanding recreational activities (e.g., swimming or cycling)?	Was u beperkt in het uitoefenen van lichamelijke zware recreatieve activiteiten (bv. zwemmen of fietsen)?
Were you limited in doing either your work or other daily activities?	Was u beperkt bij het doen van uw werk of andere dagelijkse bezigheden?
Have you been limited in doing heavy housework (e.g., washing floors or vacuuming)?	Was u beperkt in het uitvoeren van zware huishoudelijke taken (bv. de vloer schrobben of stofzuigen)?

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Were you limited in pursuing your hobbies or other leisure time activities?	Was u beperkt bij het uitoefenen van uw hobby's of bij andere bezigheden die u in uw vrije tijd doet?
Did pain interfere with your daily activities?	Heeft pijn u gehinderd bij uw dagelijkse bezigheden?
Have you had pain?	Heeft u pijn gehad?
Has pain interfered with your social activities?	Heeft pijn uw sociale activiteiten in de weg gestaan?
Has pain made it difficult for you to do the jobs that you usually do around the house?	Heeft pijn het u moeilijk gemaakt om uw gebruikelijke taken in en rond het huis uit te voeren?
Have you had severe pain?	Heeft u hevige pijn gehad?
Were you tired?	Bent u moe geweest?
Have you felt weak?	Heeft u zich slap gevoeld?
Have you felt exhausted?	Heeft u zich uitgeput gevoeld?
Have you become easily tired?	Werd u gemakkelijk moe?
Have you lacked energy?	Had u een gebrek aan energie?
Have you required frequent or long periods of rest?	Heeft u regelmatige of langere periodes van rust nodig gehad?
Have you had a feeling of overwhelming and prolonged lack of energy?	Heeft u het gevoel gehad dat u een overweldigend en langdurig gebrek aan energie had?
Have you had trouble sleeping?	Heeft u moeite met slapen gehad?
Have you had trouble getting a good night's sleep?	Heeft u moeite gehad om een goede nachtrust te hebben?
Have you had trouble staying asleep?	Heeft u moeite gehad om door te slapen?
Have you woken up for long periods during the night?	Bent u 's nachts langere periodes wakker gebleven?
Have you forced yourself to eat?	Heeft u zichzelf gedwongen om te eten?
Have you lacked appetite?	Heeft u gebrek aan eetlust gehad?
Have you lacked interest in eating?	Heeft u een gebrek aan belangstelling om te eten gehad?
Have you felt nauseated?	Heeft u zich misselijk gevoeld?
Have you vomited?	Heeft u overgegeven?
Has nausea or vomiting been a problem for you?	Is misselijkheid of overgeven een probleem voor u geweest?
Has nausea or vomiting interfered with your physical activities like taking a walk?	Heeft misselijkheid of overgeven uw lichamelijke activiteiten belemmerd, zoals een wandeling maken?
Have you been constipated?	Had u last van obstipatie (was u verstopt)?

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Have you had stools that were too hard to pass?	Heeft u ontlasting gehad die te hard was om uw behoefte te doen?
Have your stools been so hard that they were painful to pass?	Heeft u ontlasting gehad die zo hard was dat naar de WC gaan pijnlijk was?
Were you short of breath?	Bent u kortademig geweest?
Did you have severe shortness of breath?	Bent u erg buiten adem geweest?
Were you short of breath when walking more than 100 m (100 yds)?	Was u buiten adem wanneer u meer dan 100 meter liep?
Were you short of breath when walking less than 100 m (100 yds)?	Was u buiten adem wanneer u minder dan 100 meter liep?
Did you feel tense?	Heeft u zich gespannen gevoeld?
Have you felt vulnerable?	Heeft u zich kwetsbaar gevoeld?
Have you felt that nothing could cheer you up?	Heeft u het gevoel gehad dat niets u kon opvrolijken?
Have you felt miserable?	Heeft u zich ellendig gevoeld?
Did you feel depressed?	Heeft u zich neerslachtig gevoeld?
Did you worry?	Maakte u zich zorgen?
Have you felt sad?	Heeft u zich verdrietig gevoeld?
Have you been watching yourself closely for any new symptoms?	Heeft u zich nauwkeurig gecontroleerd op het voorkomen van nieuwe symptomen?
To what extent have you been troubled with side-effects from your treatment?	In hoeverre heeft u last gehad van bijwerkingen van uw behandeling?
Have you worried about recurrence of your disease?	Heeft u zich zorgen gemaakt over het eventueel terugkeren van de ziekte?
Have you been afraid of tumor progression?	Bent u bang geweest voor progressie van uw tumor?
Have you worried about your health in the future?	Heeft u zich zorgen gemaakt over uw gezondheid in de toekomst?
How much has your disease been a burden to you?	In welke mate is uw ziekte een belasting voor u geweest?
Because of your experience with cancer, have you had to limit your life plans or goals?	Heeft u uw levensplannen of levensdoelen moeten inperken?
I have felt at peace with myself	Voelde ik me innerlijk rustig
Have you had difficulty remembering things?	Heeft u moeite gehad met het zich herinneren van dingen?
Have you had difficulty in concentrating on things, like reading a newspaper or watching television?	Heeft u moeite gehad met het concentreren op dingen, zoals een krant lezen of televisie kijken?
Have you been forgetful?	Bent u vergeetachtig geweest?
Have you had difficulty remembering what someone just told you?	Heeft u moeite gehad om u te herinneren wat iemand u net vertelde?

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Have you had difficulty maintaining concentration even when doing something important?	Heeft u moeite gehad om geconcentreerd te blijven zelfs terwijl u iets belangrijks deed?
As a result of your physical condition or medical treatment, have you preferred to spend time alone?	Heeft u als gevolg van uw lichamelijke toestand of medische behandeling de voorkeur gehad om tijd alleen door te brengen?
As a result of your physical condition or medical treatment have you been less able to see your family or friends?	Bent u als gevolg van uw lichamelijke toestand of medische behandeling minder in staat geweest om uw familie of vrienden te zien?
As a result of your physical condition or medical treatment, have you spent less time with your family or friends?	Heeft u als gevolg van uw lichamelijke toestand of medische behandeling minder tijd met uw familie of vrienden doorgebracht?
As a result of your physical condition or medical treatment, have you felt isolated from your family or friends?	Heeft u zich als gevolg van uw lichamelijke toestand of medische behandeling afgezonderd gevoeld van uw familie en vrienden?
As a result of your physical condition or medical treatment, have you found it hard to make contact with people?	Heeft u als gevolg van uw lichamelijke toestand of medische behandeling het moeilijk gevonden om contact te maken met mensen?
Has your physical condition or medical treatment interfered with your family life?	Heeft uw lichamelijke toestand of medische behandeling uw familielevens in de weg gestaan?
Has your physical condition or medical treatment interfered with your social activities?	Heeft uw lichamelijke toestand of medische behandeling u belemmerd bij uw sociale bezigheden?
Has your physical condition or medical treatment interfered with your relationships with your family or friends?	Heeft uw lichamelijke toestand of medische behandeling uw relaties met familie of vrienden belemmerd?
Have you been dissatisfied with your physical appearance?	Bent u ontevreden geweest over hoe uw lichaam eruitziet?
Has the disease or treatment affected your sex life (for the worse)?	Heeft de ziekte of behandeling invloed gehad op uw seksleven?
Have you worried about your ability to have children?	Heeft u zich zorgen gemaakt over uw mogelijkheid om kinderen te krijgen?
Have you worried that you are a burden to other people	Heeft u zich zorgen gemaakt dat u anderen tot last zult zijn?
Have you worried about becoming dependent on others?	Heeft u zich zorgen gemaakt afhankelijk te worden van anderen door uw ziekte?
Has your physical condition or medical treatment caused you financial difficulties?	Heeft uw lichamelijke toestand of medische behandeling financiële moeilijkheden met zich meegebracht?
Has your physical condition or medical treatment caused you financial difficulties leading to changes in your lifestyle?	Heeft uw lichamelijke toestand of medische behandeling financiële moeilijkheden veroorzaakt, waardoor u uw levensstijl moest aanpassen?

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As a result of your physical condition or medical treatment, have you had less money to spend on yourself (e.g., for buying yourself something that you would like to have but don't necessarily need)?	Heeft u als gevolg van uw lichamelijke toestand of medische behandeling minder geld gehad om iets voor uzelf te kopen (bijv. om iets voor uzelf te kopen dat u graag wilt hebben maar niet echt nodig heeft)?
As a result of your physical condition or medical treatment, have you had difficulties paying any of your regular expenses (e.g. rent, insurance, phone)?	Heeft u als gevolg van uw lichamelijke toestand of medische behandeling moeite gehad om uw vaste lasten te betalen (bijv. huur, verzekering, telefoonrekening)?
Since the diagnosis and treatment of your cancer: Have you had problems with obtaining insurance, loans, and/or a mortgage?	Sinds de diagnose en behandeling van uw kanker: Heeft u problemen gehad met het verkrijgen van verzekeringen, leningen en/of een hypotheek?
Since the diagnosis and treatment of your cancer: Have you received support from your employer e.g. arranging flexible working?	Sinds de diagnose en behandeling van uw kanker: Heeft u ondersteuning gekregen van uw werkgever, b.v. het regelen van flexibel werken?
Since the diagnosis and treatment of your cancer: Have you made positive lifestyle changes (e.g., more exercise, healthy food, cutting down smoking)?	Sinds de diagnose en behandeling van uw kanker: Heeft u uw levensstijl op een positieve manier veranderd (bv. meer lichaamsbeweging, gezond eten, minder roken)?
<u>For the following questions please circle the number between 1 and 7 that best applies to you.</u>	Wilt u voor de volgende vragen het getal tussen 1 en 7 omcirkelen dat het meest op u van toepassing is?
How would you rate your overall quality of life during the past week?	Hoe zou u uw algehele "kwaliteit van het leven" gedurende de afgelopen week beoordelen?
How would you rate your overall health during the past week?	Hoe zou u uw algehele gezondheid gedurende de afgelopen week beoordelen?
Have you had any other significant symptoms or problems that have not been mentioned in the questions above?	Heeft u andere belangrijke symptomen of problemen gehad die niet in bovenstaande vragen zijn genoemd?
Yes. Please write down the most important ones (up to three), and rate to what extent you have experienced these symptoms or problems during the past week:	Ja. Noteer de belangrijkste (maximaal drie) en geef aan in welke mate u deze symptomen of problemen gedurende de afgelopen week heeft ervaren:
<u>During the past week, to what extent have you experienced:</u>	<u>In welke mate heeft u gedurende de afgelopen week het volgende ervaren:</u>
Symptom/problem A:	Symptoom/probleem A:
Symptom/problem B:	Symptoom/probleem B:
Symptom/problem C:	Symptoom/probleem C:

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<u>We are interested in your MOST RECENT experience of the care you have received and the communication you have had with the professional(s) who treat you.</u>	<u>Wij zijn geïnteresseerd in uw MEEST RECENTE ervaring met de zorg die u heeft ontvangen en de communicatie die u heeft gehad met uw zorgverlener(s).</u>
Have you been satisfied with your communication with your professional(s)?	Bent u tevreden over de communicatie met uw zorgverlener(s)?
Have your professional(s) spent enough time talking with you?	Nam(en) uw zorgverlener(s) voldoende tijd om met u te praten?
Have your professional(s) used language that you understand (avoided medical jargon, used clear terms)?	Gebruikte(n) uw zorgverlener(s) begrijpelijke taal (medische termen vermeden, duidelijke bewoordingen gebruikt)?
Have your professional(s) taken into account how you prefer to receive information?	Hield(en) uw zorgverlener(s) er rekening mee hoe u de informatie wilde ontvangen?
Have you felt that you and your professional(s) had a shared understanding of your disease and treatment?	Had u het gevoel dat u en uw zorgverlener(s) dezelfde opvatting hadden over uw aandoening en behandeling?
My decisions about care and treatment have been respected by my professional(s)	Mijn beslissingen over zorg en behandeling zijn gerespecteerd door mijn zorgverlener(s)
I have been given the opportunity to discuss my treatment plan with my professional(s)	Ik heb de mogelijkheid gekregen om mijn behandelplan te bespreken met mijn zorgverlener(s)
Have you felt satisfied with the care you have received?	Was u tevreden met de zorg die u heeft gekregen?
Have you felt satisfied with the information you have received (e.g. about the disease and its treatment)?	Was u tevreden met de informatie die u heeft gekregen (bijvoorbeeld over de ziekte of over de behandeling)?
<u>During the past 4 weeks:</u>	<u>Gedurende de afgelopen 4 weken:</u>
My medical appointments have interfered with my work / household activities	Mijn medische afspraken hebben mij gehinderd in mijn werk/huishoudelijke activiteiten
My medical appointments have caused problems for my family / carer	Mijn medische afspraken hebben problemen veroorzaakt voor mijn familie/verzorger
<u>How would you rate the services and care organisation of the most recent care you have received, in terms of:</u>	<u>Hoe beoordeelt u de diensten en organisatie van de meest recente zorg die u hebt ontvangen, in termen van:</u>
The provision of follow-up by the different caregivers (doctors, nurses, physiotherapists, psychologists, etc.) after treatment?	Het aanbieden van follow-up door de verschillende zorgverleners (artsen, verpleegkundigen, fysiotherapeuten, psychologen, enz.) na de behandeling?

4.1.2. English-French

Items - English	French
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<p><u>We are interested in some things about you and your health. Please answer all of the questions yourself by SELECTING the number that best applies to you. There are no "right" or "wrong" answers.</u></p>	<p><u>Nous nous intéressons à vous et à votre santé. Répondez vous-même à toutes les questions en sélectionnant le numéro qui correspond le mieux à votre situation. Il n'y a pas de réponse juste ou fausse. Ces informations sont strictement confidentielles.</u></p>
<p>Do you have any trouble doing strenuous activities, like carrying a heavy shopping bag or a suitcase?</p>	<p>Avez-vous des difficultés à faire certains efforts physiques pénibles comme porter un sac à provisions chargé ou une valise?</p>
<p>Do you have any trouble taking a long walk?</p>	<p>Avez-vous des difficultés à faire une longue promenade ?</p>
<p>Do you need help caring for your feet (e.g. cutting your toenails)?</p>	<p>Avez-vous besoin d'aide pour prendre soin de vos pieds (p. ex. pour vous couper les ongles des orteils) ?</p>
<p>Do you have any trouble carrying a heavy bag upstairs?</p>	<p>Avez-vous des difficultés à monter un sac lourd à l'étage ?</p>
<p>Do you have any trouble taking a long walk carrying a heavy pack on your back (e.g. a filled rucksack)?</p>	<p>Avez-vous des difficultés à faire une longue marche en portant une charge lourde sur le dos (p. ex. un sac à dos plein) ?</p>
<p>Do you have any trouble taking a short walk outside of the house?</p>	<p>Avez-vous des difficultés à faire un petit tour dehors ?</p>
<p>Do you need help undressing?</p>	<p>Avez-vous besoin d'aide pour vous déshabiller ?</p>
<p>Do you have any trouble walking for 30 min.?</p>	<p>Avez-vous des difficultés à marcher pendant 30 minutes ?</p>
<p><u>During the past week:</u></p>	<p><u>Au cours de la semaine passée :</u></p>
<p>Have you been limited in doing light housework (e.g. dusting or making the bed)?</p>	<p>Avez-vous été gêné(e) dans la réalisation de petits travaux ménagers (p. ex. faire la poussière ou le lit) ?</p>
<p>Have you been limited in doing physically demanding recreational activities (e.g., swimming or cycling)?</p>	<p>Avez-vous été gêné(e) dans la réalisation d'activités de loisirs physiquement exigeantes (p. ex. nager ou faire du vélo) ?</p>
<p>Were you limited in doing either your work or other daily activities?</p>	<p>Avez-vous été gêné(e) pour faire votre travail ou vos activités de tous les jours ?</p>
<p>Have you been limited in doing heavy housework (e.g., washing floors or vacuuming)?</p>	<p>Avez-vous été gêné(e) dans la réalisation de gros travaux ménagers (p. ex. laver le sol ou passer l'aspirateur) ?</p>
<p>Were you limited in pursuing your hobbies or other leisure time activities?</p>	<p>Avez-vous été gêné(e) dans vos activités de loisirs ?</p>
<p>Did pain interfere with your daily activities?</p>	<p>Des douleurs ont-elles perturbé vos activités quotidiennes ?</p>
<p>Have you had pain?</p>	<p>Avez-vous ressenti de la douleur ?</p>
<p>Has pain interfered with your social activities?</p>	<p>Vos douleurs ont-elles perturbé vos activités sociales ?</p>

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Has pain made it difficult for you to do the jobs that you usually do around the house?	Avez-vous eu des difficultés à effectuer les tâches que vous avez l'habitude de faire chez vous à cause de vos douleurs ?
Have you had severe pain?	Avez-vous ressenti des douleurs intenses ?
Were you tired?	Avez-vous été fatigué(e) ?
Have you felt weak?	Vous êtes-vous senti(e) faible ?
Have you felt exhausted?	Vous êtes-vous senti(e) épuisé(e) ?
Have you become easily tired?	Vous êtes-vous senti(e) facilement fatigué(e) ?
Have you lacked energy?	Avez-vous manqué d'énergie ?
Have you required frequent or long periods of rest?	Avez-vous ressenti des besoins de repos fréquents ou longs ?
Have you had a feeling of overwhelming and prolonged lack of energy?	Vous êtes-vous senti(e) accablé(e) par un manque d'énergie prolongé ?
Have you had trouble sleeping?	Avez-vous eu des difficultés à dormir ?
Have you had trouble getting a good night's sleep?	Avez-vous eu des difficultés à passer une bonne nuit de sommeil ?
Have you had trouble staying asleep?	Avez-vous eu du mal à rester endormi(e) ?
Have you woken up for long periods during the night?	Êtes-vous resté éveillé(e) durant de longues périodes pendant la nuit ?
Have you forced yourself to eat?	Vous êtes-vous forcé(e) à manger ?
Have you lacked appetite?	Avez-vous manqué d'appétit ?
Have you lacked interest in eating?	Avez-vous ressenti un manque d'intérêt pour la nourriture ?
Have you felt nauseated?	Avez-vous eu des nausées (mal au cœur) ?
Have you vomited?	Avez-vous vomi ?
Has nausea or vomiting been a problem for you?	Les nausées ou les vomissements ont-ils été un problème pour vous ?
Has nausea or vomiting interfered with your physical activities like taking a walk?	Les nausées ou les vomissements ont-ils perturbé vos activités physiques, comme faire une promenade ?
Have you been constipated?	Avez-vous été constipé(e) ?
Have you had stools that were too hard to pass?	Avez-vous eu des selles qui étaient trop dures pour être éliminées ?
Have your stools been so hard that they were painful to pass?	Vos selles ont-elles été dures au point d'être douloureuses à éliminer ?
Were you short of breath?	Avez-vous été essoufflé(e) ?
Did you have severe shortness of breath?	Avez-vous eu un essoufflement sévère ?
Were you short of breath when walking more than 100 m (100 yds)?	Avez-vous eu le souffle court en marchant plus de 100m ?
Were you short of breath when walking less than 100 m (100 yds)?	Avez-vous eu le souffle court en marchant moins de 100m ?

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Did you feel tense?	Vous êtes-vous senti(e) tendu(e) ?
Have you felt vulnerable?	Vous êtes-vous senti(e) vulnérable ?
Have you felt that nothing could cheer you up?	Avez-vous eu le sentiment que rien ne pouvait vous remonter le moral ?
Have you felt miserable?	Vous êtes-vous senti(e) profondément malheureux(-se) ?
Did you feel depressed?	Vous êtes-vous senti(e) déprimé(e) ?
Did you worry?	Vous êtes-vous fait du souci ?
Have you felt sad?	Vous êtes-vous senti(e) triste ?
Have you been watching yourself closely for any new symptoms?	Vous êtes-vous observé(e) de près pour détecter d'éventuels nouveaux symptômes ?
To what extent have you been troubled with side-effects from your treatment?	Dans quelle mesure avez-vous été gêné(e) par les effets secondaires de votre traitement ?
Have you worried about recurrence of your disease?	Vous êtes-vous inquiété(e) d'une récurrence éventuelle de la maladie ?
Have you been afraid of tumor progression?	Avez-vous eu peur d'une progression tumorale ?
Have you worried about your health in the future?	Vous êtes-vous inquiété(e) de votre santé pour l'avenir ?
How much has your disease been a burden to you?	À quel point votre maladie vous a-t-elle pesé ?
Because of your experience with cancer, have you had to limit your life plans or goals?	Avez-vous été obligé(e) de limiter vos projets ou vos objectifs de vie ?
I have felt at peace with myself	Je me suis senti(e) en paix avec moi-même.
Have you had difficulty remembering things?	Avez-vous eu des difficultés à vous souvenir de certaines choses ?
Have you had difficulty in concentrating on things, like reading a newspaper or watching television?	Avez-vous eu des difficultés à vous concentrer sur certaines choses, par exemple, pour lire le journal ou regarder la télévision ?
Have you been forgetful?	Vous est-il arrivé d'avoir des trous de mémoire ?
Have you had difficulty remembering what someone just told you?	Avez-vous éprouvé des difficultés à vous souvenir de ce qu'une personne venait de vous dire ?
Have you had difficulty maintaining concentration even when doing something important?	Avez-vous éprouvé des difficultés à rester concentré(e) même lorsque vous faisiez quelque chose d'important ?
As a result of your physical condition or medical treatment, have you preferred to spend time alone?	À cause de votre état physique ou de votre traitement médical, avez-vous préféré passer du temps seul(e) ?
As a result of your physical condition or medical treatment have you been less able to see your family or friends?	En raison de votre état physique ou de votre traitement médical, avez-vous été moins en mesure de voir votre famille ou vos amis ?

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As a result of your physical condition or medical treatment, have you spent less time with your family or friends?	À cause de votre état physique ou de votre traitement médical, avez-vous passé moins de temps avec votre famille ou vos amis ?
As a result of your physical condition or medical treatment, have you felt isolated from your family or friends?	À cause de votre état physique ou de votre traitement médical, vous êtes-vous senti(e) isolé(e) de votre famille ou de vos amis ?
As a result of your physical condition or medical treatment, have you found it hard to make contact with people?	À cause de votre état physique ou de votre traitement médical, avez-vous eu des difficultés à entrer en contact avec les gens ?
Has your physical condition or medical treatment interfered with your family life?	Votre état physique ou votre traitement médical vous ont-ils gêné(e) dans votre vie familiale ?
Has your physical condition or medical treatment interfered with your social activities?	Votre état physique ou votre traitement médical vous ont-ils gêné(e) dans vos activités sociales (par exemple, sortir avec des amis, aller au cinéma...) ?
Has your physical condition or medical treatment interfered with your relationships with your family or friends?	Votre état physique ou votre traitement médical vous ont-ils gêné(e) dans vos relations avec votre famille ou vos amis ?
Have you been dissatisfied with your physical appearance?	Avez-vous été mécontent(e) de votre apparence physique ?
Has the disease or treatment affected your sex life (for the worse)?	La maladie ou son traitement ont-ils eu un impact défavorable sur votre vie sexuelle ?
Have you worried about your ability to have children?	Vous êtes-vous inquiété(e) de pouvoir avoir des enfants ?
Have you worried that you are a burden to other people	Vous êtes-vous inquiété(e) d'être un fardeau pour les autres ?
Have you worried about becoming dependent on others?	Avez-vous été inquiet(ète) de devenir dépendant des autres du fait de votre maladie ?
Has your physical condition or medical treatment caused you financial difficulties?	Votre état physique ou votre traitement médical vous ont-ils causé des problèmes financiers ?
Has your physical condition or medical treatment caused you financial difficulties leading to changes in your lifestyle?	Votre état physique ou votre traitement médical ont-ils entraîné des problèmes financiers ayant conduit à des changements de votre style de vie ?
As a result of your physical condition or medical treatment, have you had less money to spend on yourself (e.g., for buying yourself something that you would like to have but don't necessarily need)?	À cause de votre état physique ou de votre traitement médical, avez-vous eu moins d'argent à vous consacrer (p. ex. pour vous acheter quelque chose que vous aimeriez avoir mais dont vous n'avez pas nécessairement besoin) ?
As a result of your physical condition or medical treatment, have you had difficulties paying any of your regular expenses (e.g. rent, insurance, phone)?	À cause de votre état physique ou de votre traitement médical, avez-vous eu des difficultés à payer vos dépenses courantes (p. ex. le loyer, l'assurance, le téléphone) ?

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Since the diagnosis and treatment of your cancer: Have you had problems with obtaining insurance, loans, and/or a mortgage?	Depuis le diagnostic et le traitement de votre cancer: Avez-vous eu des difficultés avec (pour obtenir) une assurance, un prêt ou un emprunt immobilier ?
Since the diagnosis and treatment of your cancer: Have you received support from your employer e.g. arranging flexible working?	Depuis le diagnostic et le traitement de votre cancer: Avez-vous reçu du soutien de votre employeur par exemple pour organiser votre travail de manière flexible?
Since the diagnosis and treatment of your cancer: Have you made positive lifestyle changes (e.g., more exercise, healthy food, cutting down smoking)?	Depuis le diagnostic et le traitement de votre cancer: Avez-vous apporté des changements positifs dans votre style de vie (p. ex. plus d'exercice, alimentation plus saine, fumer moins) ?
<u>For the following questions please circle the number between 1 and 7 that best applies to you.</u>	<u>Pour les questions suivantes, veuillez répondre en entourant le chiffre entre 1 et 7 qui s'applique le mieux à votre situation :</u>
How would you rate your overall quality of life during the past week?	Comment évalueriez-vous votre état de santé au cours de la semaine passée ?
How would you rate your overall health during the past week?	Comment évalueriez-vous l'ensemble de votre qualité de vie au cours de la semaine passée ?
Have you had any other significant symptoms or problems that have not been mentioned in the questions above?	Avez-vous eu d'autres symptômes ou problèmes significatifs qui n'auraient pas été mentionnés dans les questions ci-dessus ?
Yes. Please write down the most important ones (up to three), and rate to what extent you have experienced these symptoms or problems during the past week:	Oui. Veuillez noter les plus importants (trois maximum) et évaluer dans quelle mesure vous avez été affecté(e) par ces symptômes ou problèmes au cours de la semaine passée.
<u>During the past week, to what extent have you experienced:</u>	<u>Au cours de la semaine passée, dans quelle mesure avez-vous été affecté(e) par :</u>
Symptom/problem A:	Symptôme/problème A :
Symptom/problem B:	Symptôme/problème B :
Symptom/problem C:	Symptôme/problème C :
<u>We are interested in your MOST RECENT experience of the care you have received and the communication you have had with the professional(s) who treat you.</u>	<u>Nous nous intéressons à votre expérience la plus récente des soins que vous avez reçu et à la communication avec le(s) professionnel(s) qui vous soignent.</u>
Have you been satisfied with your communication with your professional(s)?	Avez-vous été satisfait(e) de votre communication avec vos professionnels de santé ?
Have your professional(s) spent enough time talking with you?	Votre (vos) professionnel(s) a-t-il (ont-ils) passé suffisamment de temps à échanger avec vous ?

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Have your professional(s) used language that you understand (avoided medical jargon, used clear terms)?	Votre (vos) professionnel(s) a-t-il (ont-ils) utilisé un langage que vous comprenez (éviter le jargon médical, utiliser des termes clairs)?
Have your professional(s) taken into account how you prefer to receive information?	Votre (vos) professionnel(s) a-t-il (ont-ils) pris en compte la façon dont vous préférez recevoir des informations?
Have you felt that you and your professional(s) had a shared understanding of your disease and treatment?	Avez-vous eu l'impression d'avoir le même point de vue que vos professionnels de santé sur votre maladie et votre traitement ?
My decisions about care and treatment have been respected by my professional(s)	Mes décisions en matière de soins et de traitement ont été respectées par mon (mes) professionnel(s)
I have been given the opportunity to discuss my treatment plan with my professional(s)	J'ai eu la possibilité de discuter de mon plan de traitement avec mon (mes) professionnel(s)
Have you felt satisfied with the care you have received?	Avez-vous été satisfait(e) des soins reçus ?
Have you felt satisfied with the information you have received (e.g. about the disease and its treatment)?	Avez-vous été satisfait(e) de la quantité d'informations reçues (p. ex. sur votre maladie et son traitement) ?
During the past 4 weeks:	Au cours des 4 dernières semaines
My medical appointments have interfered with my work / household activities	Mes rendez-vous médicaux ont causé des problèmes à mon travail/mes activités domestiques
My medical appointments have caused problems for my family / carer	Mes rendez-vous médicaux ont causé des problèmes à ma famille ou à mon proche.
<u>How would you rate the services and care organisation of the most recent care you have received, in terms of:</u>	<u>Dans l'unité ambulatoire de cet hôpital, comment évalueriez-vous l'organisation des services et des soins concernant :</u>
The provision of follow-up by the different caregivers (doctors, nurses, physiotherapists, psychologists, etc.) after treatment?	Le suivi assuré par les différents soignants (ex : médecins, infirmier(-ère)s, kinésithérapeutes, psychologues, etc.) après le traitement ?

4.1.3. English-German

Items - English	German
<u>We are interested in some things about you and your health. Please answer all of the questions yourself by SELECTING the number that best</u>	<u>Wir sind an einigen Angaben interessiert, die Sie und Ihre Gesundheit betreffen. Bitte beantworten Sie die folgenden Fragen selbst, indem Sie die Zahl wählen, die am besten auf</u>

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<u>applies to you. There are no "right" or "wrong" answers.</u>	<u>Sie zutrifft. Es gibt keine „richtigen“ oder „falschen“ Antworten. Ihre Angaben werden streng vertraulich behandelt.</u>
Do you have any trouble doing strenuous activities, like carrying a heavy shopping bag or a suitcase?	Bereitet es Ihnen Schwierigkeiten sich körperlich anzustrengen (z. B. eine schwere Einkaufstasche oder einen Koffer zu tragen)?
Do you have any trouble taking a long walk?	Bereitet es Ihnen Schwierigkeiten, einen längeren Spaziergang zu machen?
Do you need help caring for your feet (e.g. cutting your toenails)?	Benötigen Sie Hilfe bei der Fußpflege (z. B. beim Schneiden der Zehennägel)?
Do you have any trouble carrying a heavy bag upstairs?	Bereitet es Ihnen Schwierigkeiten, eine schwere Tasche die Treppe hoch zu tragen?
Do you have any trouble taking a long walk carrying a heavy pack on your back (e.g. a filled rucksack)?	Bereitet es Ihnen Schwierigkeiten, mit einer schweren Last (z. B. einem vollen Rucksack) auf dem Rücken eine lange Strecke zu gehen?
Do you have any trouble taking a short walk outside of the house?	Bereitet es Ihnen Schwierigkeiten, eine kurze Strecke außer Haus zu gehen?
Do you need help undressing?	Benötigen Sie Hilfe beim Ausziehen?
Do you have any trouble walking for 30 min.?	Bereitet es Ihnen Schwierigkeiten, 30 Minuten zu gehen?
<u>During the past week:</u>	<u>Während der letzten Woche:</u>
Have you been limited in doing light housework (e.g. dusting or making the bed)?	Waren Sie bei leichten Hausarbeiten eingeschränkt (z. B. Staubwischen oder Betten machen)?
Have you been limited in doing physically demanding recreational activities (e.g., swimming or cycling)?	Waren Sie bei Freizeit- oder Sportaktivitäten eingeschränkt (z. B. Schwimmen oder Radfahren)?
Were you limited in doing either your work or other daily activities?	Waren Sie bei Ihrer Arbeit oder bei anderen tagtäglichen Beschäftigungen eingeschränkt?
Have you been limited in doing heavy housework (e.g., washing floors or vacuuming)?	Waren Sie bei schweren Hausarbeiten eingeschränkt (z. B. Böden wischen oder Staubsaugen)?
Were you limited in pursuing your hobbies or other leisure time activities?	Waren Sie bei Ihren Hobbys oder anderen Freizeitbeschäftigungen eingeschränkt?
Did pain interfere with your daily activities?	Fühlten Sie sich durch Schmerzen in Ihrem alltäglichen Leben beeinträchtigt?
Have you had pain?	Hatten Sie Schmerzen?
Has pain interfered with your social activities?	Haben Schmerzen Ihr Sozialleben beeinträchtigt?
Has pain made it difficult for you to do the jobs that you usually do around the house?	Ist es Ihnen aufgrund von Schmerzen schwergefallen, Ihre normalen Aufgaben rund ums Haus zu erledigen?
Have you had severe pain?	Hatten Sie starke Schmerzen?

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Were you tired?	Waren Sie müde?
Have you felt weak?	Fühlten Sie sich schwach?
Have you felt exhausted?	Fühlten Sie sich erschöpft?
Have you become easily tired?	Wurden Sie leicht müde?
Have you lacked energy?	Fehlte es Ihnen an Energie?
Have you required frequent or long periods of rest?	Mussten Sie sich oft bzw. über längere Zeit ausruhen?
Have you had a feeling of overwhelming and prolonged lack of energy?	Hatten Sie das Gefühl einer sehr starken und anhaltenden Energielosigkeit?
Have you had trouble sleeping?	Hatten Sie Schlafstörungen?
Have you had trouble getting a good night's sleep?	Hatten Sie Schwierigkeiten, nachts gut zu schlafen?
Have you had trouble staying asleep?	Hatten Sie Schwierigkeiten durchzuschlafen?
Have you woken up for long periods during the night?	Sind Sie nachts aufgewacht und haben längere Zeit wachgelegen?
Have you forced yourself to eat?	Haben Sie sich zum Essen gezwungen?
Have you lacked appetite?	Hatten Sie Appetitmangel?
Have you lacked interest in eating?	Hat es Ihnen an Interesse am Essen gefehlt?
Have you felt nauseated?	War Ihnen übel?
Have you vomited?	Haben Sie erbrochen?
Has nausea or vomiting been a problem for you?	War Übelkeit oder Erbrechen ein Problem für Sie?
Has nausea or vomiting interfered with your physical activities like taking a walk?	Hat Übelkeit oder Erbrechen Sie bei Ihren körperlichen Aktivitäten beeinträchtigt, z. B. beim Spaziergehen?
Have you been constipated?	Hatten Sie Verstopfung?
Have you had stools that were too hard to pass?	War Ihr Stuhl so hart, dass Sie ihn nicht ausscheiden konnten?
Have your stools been so hard that they were painful to pass?	War Ihr Stuhl so hart, dass Sie Schmerzen bei der Ausscheidung hatten?
Were you short of breath?	Waren Sie kurzatmig?
Did you have severe shortness of breath?	Waren Sie sehr kurzatmig?
Were you short of breath when walking more than 100 m (100 yds)?	Waren Sie kurzatmig, wenn Sie mehr als 100 m zu Fuß gingen?
Were you short of breath when walking less than 100 m (100 yds)?	Waren Sie kurzatmig, wenn Sie weniger als 100 m zu Fuß gingen?
Did you feel tense?	Fühlten Sie sich angespannt?
Have you felt vulnerable?	Haben Sie sich verletzlich gefühlt?
Have you felt that nothing could cheer you up?	Hatten Sie das Gefühl, dass nichts Sie aufheitern kann?
Have you felt miserable?	Haben Sie sich elend gefühlt?

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Did you feel depressed?	Fühlten Sie sich niedergeschlagen?
Did you worry?	Haben Sie sich Sorgen gemacht?
Have you felt sad?	Haben Sie sich traurig gefühlt?
Have you been watching yourself closely for any new symptoms?	Haben Sie sich selbst genau beobachtet in Bezug auf irgendwelche neuen Symptome?
To what extent have you been troubled with side-effects from your treatment?	In welchem Ausmaß fühlten Sie sich durch Nebenwirkungen Ihrer Behandlung belästigt/beeinträchtigt?
Have you worried about recurrence of your disease?	Haben Sie sich Sorgen darüber gemacht, dass Ihre Krankheit erneut auftreten könnte?
Have you been afraid of tumor progression?	Hatten Sie Angst, dass Ihr Tumor fortschreitet?
Have you worried about your health in the future?	Haben Sie sich Sorgen um Ihre zukünftige Gesundheit gemacht?
How much has your disease been a burden to you?	Wie sehr fühlten Sie sich durch Ihre Erkrankung belastet?
Because of your experience with cancer, have you had to limit your life plans or goals?	Aufgrund Ihrer Erfahrung mit Krebs: Mussten Sie Ihre Lebenspläne oder Ziele einschränken?
I have felt at peace with myself	Ich fühlte mich mit mir selbst im Einklang
Have you had difficulty remembering things?	Hatten Sie Schwierigkeiten, sich an Dinge zu erinnern?
Have you had difficulty in concentrating on things, like reading a newspaper or watching television?	Hatten Sie Schwierigkeiten, sich auf etwas zu konzentrieren, z. B. auf das Zeitunglesen oder das Fernsehen?
Have you been forgetful?	Sind Sie vergesslich gewesen?
Have you had difficulty remembering what someone just told you?	Hatten Sie Schwierigkeiten sich zu erinnern, was jemand gerade zu Ihnen gesagt hat?
Have you had difficulty maintaining concentration even when doing something important?	Hatten Sie Schwierigkeiten konzentriert zu bleiben, selbst wenn Sie etwas Wichtiges taten?
As a result of your physical condition or medical treatment, have you preferred to spend time alone?	Haben Sie es aufgrund Ihres körperlichen Zustands oder Ihrer medizinischen Behandlung bevorzugt, Ihre Zeit alleine zu verbringen?
As a result of your physical condition or medical treatment have you been less able to see your family or friends?	War es Ihnen aufgrund Ihres körperlichen Zustands oder Ihrer medizinischen Behandlung seltener möglich, Ihre Familie oder Freunde zu sehen?
As a result of your physical condition or medical treatment, have you spent less time with your family or friends?	Haben Sie aufgrund Ihres körperlichen Zustands oder Ihrer medizinischen Behandlung weniger Zeit mit Ihrer Familie oder Freunden verbracht?

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As a result of your physical condition or medical treatment, have you felt isolated from your family or friends?	Haben Sie sich aufgrund Ihres körperlichen Zustands oder Ihrer medizinischen Behandlung von Ihrer Familie oder Freunden isoliert gefühlt?
As a result of your physical condition or medical treatment, have you found it hard to make contact with people?	Fanden Sie es aufgrund Ihres körperlichen Zustands oder Ihrer medizinischen Behandlung schwierig, mit Menschen in Kontakt zu kommen?
Has your physical condition or medical treatment interfered with your family life?	Hat Ihr körperlicher Zustand oder Ihre medizinische Behandlung Ihr Familienleben beeinträchtigt?
Has your physical condition or medical treatment interfered with your social activities?	Hat Ihr körperlicher Zustand oder Ihre medizinische Behandlung Ihr Zusammensein oder Ihre gemeinsamen Unternehmungen mit anderen Menschen beeinträchtigt?
Has your physical condition or medical treatment interfered with your relationships with your family or friends?	Hat Ihr körperlicher Zustand oder Ihre medizinische Behandlung die Beziehung zu Ihrer Familie oder Freunden gestört?
Have you been dissatisfied with your physical appearance?	Waren Sie unzufrieden mit Ihrer äußeren Erscheinung?
Has the disease or treatment affected your sex life (for the worse)?	Hat die Krankheit oder Behandlung Ihr Sexualleben beeinflusst? (zum Schlechten)
Have you worried about your ability to have children?	Haben Sie sich Sorgen darüber gemacht, ob Sie noch Kinder bekommen bzw. zeugen können?
Have you worried that you are a burden to other people	Haben Sie sich Sorgen darüber gemacht, anderen zur Last zu fallen?
Have you worried about becoming dependent on others?	Haben Sie sich Sorgen darüber gemacht, dass Sie von anderen abhängig werden könnten?
Has your physical condition or medical treatment caused you financial difficulties?	Hat Ihr körperlicher Zustand oder Ihre medizinische Behandlung für Sie finanzielle Schwierigkeiten mit sich gebracht?
Has your physical condition or medical treatment caused you financial difficulties leading to changes in your lifestyle?	Sind Sie aufgrund Ihres körperlichen Zustands oder Ihrer medizinischen Behandlung in finanzielle Schwierigkeiten geraten, durch die sich Ihr Lebensstil geändert hat?
As a result of your physical condition or medical treatment, have you had less money to spend on yourself (e.g., for buying yourself something that you would like to have but don't necessarily need)?	Haben Sie aufgrund Ihres körperlichen Zustands oder Ihrer medizinischen Behandlung weniger Geld gehabt, das Sie für sich selbst ausgeben konnten (z. B. um sich Dinge zu kaufen, die Sie gerne hätten, aber nicht unbedingt brauchen)?
As a result of your physical condition or medical treatment, have you had difficulties paying any of your regular expenses (e.g. rent, insurance, phone)?	Haben Sie aufgrund Ihres körperlichen Zustands oder Ihrer medizinischen Behandlung Schwierigkeiten gehabt, Ihre regelmäßigen Ausgaben zu bezahlen (z. B. Miete, Versicherungen, Telefon)?

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Since the diagnosis and treatment of your cancer: Have you had problems with obtaining insurance, loans, and/or a mortgage?	Seit der Diagnose und der Behandlung Ihrer Krebserkrankung: Hatten Sie Probleme mit einer Versicherung, Krediten und/oder einer Hypothek (diese abzuschließen)?
Since the diagnosis and treatment of your cancer: Have you received support from your employer e.g. arranging flexible working?	Seit der Diagnose und der Behandlung Ihrer Krebserkrankung: Haben Sie von Ihrem Arbeitgeber Unterstützung erhalten, z. B. bei der Vereinbarung flexibler Arbeitszeiten?
Since the diagnosis and treatment of your cancer: Have you made positive lifestyle changes (e.g., more exercise, healthy food, cutting down smoking)?	Seit der Diagnose und der Behandlung Ihrer Krebserkrankung: Haben Sie Ihren Lebensstil positiv geändert (z. B. mehr Bewegung, gesundes Essen, das Rauchen eingeschränkt)?
<u>For the following questions please circle the number between 1 and 7 that best applies to you.</u>	<u>Bitte kreisen Sie bei den folgenden Fragen die Zahl zwischen 1 und 7 ein, die am besten auf Sie zutrifft:</u>
How would you rate your overall quality of life during the past week?	Wie würden Sie insgesamt Ihre Lebensqualität während der letzten Woche einschätzen?
How would you rate your overall health during the past week?	Wie würden Sie insgesamt Ihren Gesundheitszustand während der letzten Woche einschätzen?
Have you had any other significant symptoms or problems that have not been mentioned in the questions above?	Sind bei Ihnen andere erhebliche Symptome oder Probleme aufgetreten, die in den Fragen oben nicht erwähnt wurden?
Yes. Please write down the most important ones (up to three), and rate to what extent you have experienced these symptoms or problems during the past week:	Ja. Notieren Sie bitte die wichtigsten (bis zu drei) und bewerten Sie, inwieweit diese Symptome oder Probleme in der letzten Woche bei Ihnen aufgetreten sind:
<u>During the past week, to what extent have you experienced:</u>	<u>Inwieweit ist bei Ihnen in der letzten Woche Folgendes aufgetreten:</u>
Symptom/problem A:	Symptom/problem A:
Symptom/problem B:	Symptom/problem B:
Symptom/problem C:	Symptom/problem C:
<u>We are interested in your MOST RECENT experience of the care you have received and the communication you have had with the professional(s) who treat you.</u>	<u>Wir interessieren uns für Ihre ZULETZT GEMACHTEN Erfahrungen bezüglich der Versorgung, die Sie erhalten haben, und bezüglich der Kommunikation mit Ihren Behandler/innen.</u>
Have you been satisfied with your communication with your professional(s)?	Waren Sie mit der Kommunikation mit Ihren Behandler/innen zufrieden?
Have your professional(s) spent enough time talking with you?	Haben Ihre Behandler/innen sich genug Zeit für das Gespräch mit Ihnen genommen?

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Have your professional(s) used language that you understand (avoided medical jargon, used clear terms)?	Haben Ihre Behandler/innen im Gespräch verständlich ausgedrückt (medizinische Begriffe vermieden, verständliche Ausdrücke verwendet)?
Have your professional(s) taken into account how you prefer to receive information?	Haben Ihre Behandler/innen berücksichtigt, wie Sie Informationen erhalten wollten?
Have you felt that you and your professional(s) had a shared understanding of your disease and treatment?	Hatten Sie das Gefühl, dass Sie und Ihre Behandler/innen ein gemeinsames Verständnis von Ihrer Krankheit und Behandlung hatten?
My decisions about care and treatment have been respected by my professional(s)	Meine Entscheidungen über meine Versorgung und Behandlung wurde von meinen Behandler/innen respektiert
I have been given the opportunity to discuss my treatment plan with my professional(s)	Ich habe die Gelegenheit bekommen, meinen Behandlungsplan mit meinen Behandler/innen zu besprechen
Have you felt satisfied with the care you have received?	Waren Sie mit der erhaltenen Pflege/Betreuung zufrieden?
Have you felt satisfied with the information you have received (e.g. about the disease and its treatment)?	Waren Sie mit den erhaltenen Informationen zufrieden (z.B. zur Erkankung und ihrer Therapie)?
During the past 4 weeks:	Während der letzten vier Wochen:
My medical appointments have interfered with my work / household activities	Meine Behandlungstermine haben meine Arbeit/ häuslichen Aktivitäten beeinträchtigt
My medical appointments have caused problems for my family / carer	Meine Behandlungstermine haben Probleme für meine Familie/ Pflegende verursacht
<u>How would you rate the services and care organisation of the most recent care you have received, in terms of:</u>	<u>Wie würden Sie die Dienstleistungen und die Organisation der Betreuung in der Arztpraxis, Ambulanz oder dem Krankenhaus, wo sie zuletzt behandelt wurden, bezogen auf folgende:</u>
The provision of follow-up by the different caregivers (doctors, nurses, physiotherapists, psychologists, etc.) after treatment?	Das Angebot von Nachkontrollen durch die verschiedenen Berufsgruppen (Ärzte, Pflegekräfte, Physiotherapeuten, Psychologen usw.), die in Ihre Behandlung eingebunden sind?

4.1.4. English-Italian

Items - English	Italian
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<p><u>We are interested in some things about you and your health. Please answer all of the questions yourself by SELECTING the number that best applies to you. There are no "right" or "wrong" answers.</u></p>	<p><u>Siamo interessati a conoscere alcuni aspetti della sua esperienza di cura e del suo stato di salute. La preghiamo di rispondere personalmente a tutte le domande SCEGLIENDO il numero che meglio descrive la sua condizione. Non ci sono risposte "giuste" o "sbagliate".</u></p>
<p>Do you have any trouble doing strenuous activities, like carrying a heavy shopping bag or a suitcase?</p>	<p>Ha difficoltà nello svolgere attività faticose, come portare una borsa della spesa pesante o una valigia?</p>
<p>Do you have any trouble taking a long walk?</p>	<p>Ha difficoltà nel fare una lunga passeggiata?</p>
<p>Do you need help caring for your feet (e.g. cutting your toenails)?</p>	<p>Ha bisogno di aiuto nel curarsi i piedi (ad esempio tagliarsi le unghie)?</p>
<p>Do you have any trouble carrying a heavy bag upstairs?</p>	<p>Ha difficoltà nel portare una borsa pesante al piano superiore?</p>
<p>Do you have any trouble taking a long walk carrying a heavy pack on your back (e.g. a filled rucksack)?</p>	<p>Ha difficoltà nel fare una passeggiata lunga con un carico pesante sulla schiena (ad esempio uno zaino pieno)?</p>
<p>Do you have any trouble taking a short walk outside of the house?</p>	<p>Ha difficoltà nel fare una breve passeggiata fuori casa?</p>
<p>Do you need help undressing?</p>	<p>Ha bisogno di aiuto per svestirsi?</p>
<p>Do you have any trouble walking for 30 min.?</p>	<p>Ha difficoltà nel camminare per 30 minuti?</p>
<p><u>During the past week:</u></p>	<p><u>Durante l'ultima settimana:</u></p>
<p>Have you been limited in doing light housework (e.g. dusting or making the bed)?</p>	<p>È stato/a limitato/a nello svolgere lavori domestici leggeri (ad esempio spolverare o rifare il letto)?</p>
<p>Have you been limited in doing physically demanding recreational activities (e.g., swimming or cycling)?</p>	<p>È stato/a limitato/a nello svolgere attività fisiche ricreative (ad esempio nuotare o andare in bicicletta)?</p>
<p>Were you limited in doing either your work or other daily activities?</p>	<p>Ha avuto limitazioni nel fare il Suo lavoro o altre attività quotidiane?</p>
<p>Have you been limited in doing heavy housework (e.g., washing floors or vacuuming)?</p>	<p>È stato/a limitato/a nello svolgere lavori domestici pesanti (ad esempio lavare i pavimenti o passare l'aspirapolvere)?</p>
<p>Were you limited in pursuing your hobbies or other leisure time activities?</p>	<p>Ha avuto limitazioni nel praticare i Suoi passatempi-hobby o altre attività di divertimento o svago?</p>
<p>Did pain interfere with your daily activities?</p>	<p>Il dolore ha interferito con le Sue attività quotidiane?</p>
<p>Have you had pain?</p>	<p>Ha avuto dolore?</p>
<p>Has pain interfered with your social activities?</p>	<p>Il dolore ha interferito con le Sue attività sociali?</p>

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Has pain made it difficult for you to do the jobs that you usually do around the house?	Il dolore ha reso difficile svolgere i lavori che solitamente compie in casa?
Have you had severe pain?	Ha avuto un dolore forte?
Were you tired?	Ha sentito stanchezza?
Have you felt weak?	Ha sentito debolezza?
Have you felt exhausted?	Si è sentito esausto?
Have you become easily tired?	Si è stancato/a facilmente?
Have you lacked energy?	Ha avvertito mancanza di energia?
Have you required frequent or long periods of rest?	Ha avuto necessità di periodi frequenti o prolungati di riposo?
Have you had a feeling of overwhelming and prolonged lack of energy?	Ha avvertito un'opprimente e prolungata di mancanza di energie?
Have you had trouble sleeping?	Ha avuto difficoltà a dormire?
Have you had trouble getting a good night's sleep?	Ha avuto problemi a trascorrere una notte di sonno normale?
Have you had trouble staying asleep?	Ha avuto problemi a rimanere addormentato/a?
Have you woken up for long periods during the night?	Ha avuto risvegli notturni prolungati?
Have you forced yourself to eat?	Ha mangiato in modo forzato?
Have you lacked appetite?	Le è mancato l'appetito?
Have you lacked interest in eating?	Ha perso interesse per il cibo?
Have you felt nauseated?	Ha avuto un senso di nausea?
Have you vomited?	Ha vomitato?
Has nausea or vomiting been a problem for you?	La nausea o il vomito è stato per Lei un problema?
Has nausea or vomiting interfered with your physical activities like taking a walk?	La nausea o il vomito ha interferito con le Sue attività fisiche come fare una passeggiata?
Have you been constipated?	Ha avuto problemi di stitichezza?
Have you had stools that were too hard to pass?	Ha avuto feci troppo dure per essere espulse?
Have your stools been so hard that they were painful to pass?	Le sue feci sono state così dure da causare dolore all'espulsione?
Were you short of breath?	Le è mancato il fiato?
Did you have severe shortness of breath?	Le è capitato di provare un forte accorciamento del respiro?
Were you short of breath when walking more than 100 m (100 yds)?	Si è sentito/a affannato/a dopo aver camminato per oltre 100 m?
Were you short of breath when walking less than 100 m (100 yds)?	Si è sentito/a affannato/a dopo aver camminato per meno di 100 m?
Did you feel tense?	Si è sentito(a) teso(a)?
Have you felt vulnerable?	Si è sentito/a vulnerabile?

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Have you felt that nothing could cheer you up?	Ha avuto l'impressione che niente potesse rallegrarLa?
Have you felt miserable?	Si è sentito/a infelice?
Did you feel depressed?	Ha avvertito uno stato di depressione?
Did you worry?	Ha avuto preoccupazioni?
Have you felt sad?	Si è sentito/a triste?
Have you been watching yourself closely for any new symptoms?	Ha prestato maggiore attenzione a eventuali nuovi sintomi?
To what extent have you been troubled with side-effects from your treatment?	Quanto è stato/a disturbato/a dagli effetti collaterali della terapia?
Have you worried about recurrence of your disease?	Ha temuto il ripresentarsi della malattia?
Have you been afraid of tumor progression?	Ha temuto la progressione del tumore?
Have you worried about your health in the future?	Ha avuto preoccupazioni per la Sua salute futura?
How much has your disease been a burden to you?	Quanto Le è pesata la malattia?
Because of your experience with cancer, have you had to limit your life plans or goals?	Ha dovuto limitare i Suoi obiettivi di vita o progetti?
I have felt at peace with myself	Mi sento in pace con me stesso
Have you had difficulty remembering things?	Ha avuto difficoltà a ricordare le cose?
Have you had difficulty in concentrating on things, like reading a newspaper or watching television?	Ha avuto difficoltà a concentrarsi su cose come leggere un giornale o guardare la televisione?
Have you been forgetful?	Le è capitato di dimenticare facilmente le cose?
Have you had difficulty remembering what someone just told you?	Ha avuto difficoltà a ricordare cosa Le era stato appena detto?
Have you had difficulty maintaining concentration even when doing something important?	Ha avuto difficoltà a mantenere la concentrazione, anche mentre faceva qualcosa di importante?
As a result of your physical condition or medical treatment, have you preferred to spend time alone?	A causa delle Sue condizioni fisiche o della terapia, ha preferito trascorrere tempo da solo/a?
As a result of your physical condition or medical treatment have you been less able to see your family or friends?	A causa delle Sue condizioni fisiche o della terapia, è stato/a meno in grado di vedere i Suoi familiari o gli amici?
As a result of your physical condition or medical treatment, have you spent less time with your family or friends?	A causa delle Sue condizioni fisiche o della terapia, ha trascorso meno tempo insieme ai Suoi familiari o agli amici?

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As a result of your physical condition or medical treatment, have you felt isolated from your family or friends?	A causa delle Sue condizioni fisiche o della terapia, si è sentito/a isolato/a dai Suoi familiari o dagli amici?
As a result of your physical condition or medical treatment, have you found it hard to make contact with people?	A causa delle Sue condizioni fisiche o della terapia, Le è stato difficile stabilire un contatto con le persone?
Has your physical condition or medical treatment interfered with your family life?	Le Sue condizioni fisiche o il Suo trattamento medico hanno interferito con la Sua vita familiare?
Has your physical condition or medical treatment interfered with your social activities?	Le Sue condizioni fisiche o il Suo trattamento medico hanno interferito con le Sue attività sociali?
Has your physical condition or medical treatment interfered with your relationships with your family or friends?	Le Sue condizioni fisiche o la terapia hanno interferito nei rapporti con la Sua famiglia o gli amici?
Have you been dissatisfied with your physical appearance?	Ha provato insoddisfazione per il Suo aspetto fisico?
Has the disease or treatment affected your sex life (for the worse)?	La malattia o il trattamento hanno influenzato (in negativo) la Sua vita sessuale?
Have you worried about your ability to have children?	Ha temuto di non essere in grado di avere figli?
Have you worried that you are a burden to other people	Si è preoccupato/a di diventare un peso per gli altri?
Have you worried about becoming dependent on others?	Ha temuto di diventare dipendente dagli altri?
Has your physical condition or medical treatment caused you financial difficulties?	Le Sue condizioni fisiche o il Suo trattamento medico Le hanno causato difficoltà finanziarie?
Has your physical condition or medical treatment caused you financial difficulties leading to changes in your lifestyle?	Le Sue condizioni fisiche o la terapia hanno comportato per Lei difficoltà finanziarie che L'hanno portata a modificare il Suo stile di vita?
As a result of your physical condition or medical treatment, have you had less money to spend on yourself (e.g., for buying yourself something that you would like to have but don't necessarily need)?	A causa delle Sue condizioni fisiche o della terapia, ha avuto meno denaro da spendere per sé (ad esempio per comperare qualcosa che avrebbe desiderato avere ma di cui non aveva una stretta necessità)?
As a result of your physical condition or medical treatment, have you had difficulties paying any of your regular expenses (e.g. rent, insurance, phone)?	A causa delle Sue condizioni fisiche o della terapia, ha avuto difficoltà a pagare alcune spese fisse (ad esempio affitto, assicurazione, telefono)?
Since the diagnosis and treatment of your cancer: Have you had problems with obtaining insurance, loans, and/or a mortgage?	Dalla diagnosi e dal trattamento del Suo cancro: Ha avuto problemi con assicurazioni, prestiti e/o mutui (e per ottenerli)?

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Since the diagnosis and treatment of your cancer: Have you received support from your employer e.g. arranging flexible working?	Dalla diagnosi e dal trattamento del Suo cancro: Ha ricevuto supporto dal suo datore di lavoro, per esempio la possibilità di svolgere il suo lavoro in modo flessibile?
Since the diagnosis and treatment of your cancer: Have you made positive lifestyle changes (e.g., more exercise, healthy food, cutting down smoking)?	Dalla diagnosi e dal trattamento del Suo cancro: Successivamente alla diagnosi e ai trattamenti: ha migliorato alcuni aspetti del suo stile di vita (es. maggiore esercizio fisico, alimentazione sana, riduzione del fumo)?
<u>For the following questions please circle the number between 1 and 7 that best applies to you.</u>	<u>Per le seguenti domande, la preghiamo di indicare un numero da 1 a 7 che meglio descrive la sua esperienza.</u>
How would you rate your overall quality of life during the past week?	Come valuterebbe in generale la Sua qualità di vita durante gli ultimi sette giorni?
How would you rate your overall health during the past week?	Come valuterebbe in generale la Sua salute durante gli ultimi sette giorni?
Have you had any other significant symptoms or problems that have not been mentioned in the questions above?	Ha avuto altri sintomi o problemi significativi che non sono stati citati nelle domande precedenti?
Yes. Please write down the most important ones (up to three), and rate to what extent you have experienced these symptoms or problems during the past week:	Sì. La preghiamo di indicare i più significativi (fino a un massimo di tre), e a valutare in che misura ha manifestato tali sintomi o problemi durante gli ultimi sette giorni:
<u>During the past week, to what extent have you experienced:</u>	<u>Durante gli ultimi sette giorni, in quale misura si sono manifestati:</u>
Symptom/problem A:	Sintomo/problema A
Symptom/problem B:	Sintomo/problema B
Symptom/problem C:	Sintomo/problema C
<u>We are interested in your MOST RECENT experience of the care you have received and the communication you have had with the professional(s) who treat you.</u>	<u>Siamo interessati a conoscere alcuni aspetti della sua più recente esperienza di cura e di relazione/comunicazione con gli operatori sanitari (medici, infermieri, fisioterapisti, psicologi, ecc.) che l'hanno assistita.</u>
Have you been satisfied with your communication with your professional(s)?	È rimasto/a soddisfatto/a della comunicazione tra Lei e gli operatori sanitari?
Have your professional(s) spent enough time talking with you?	Gli operatori sanitari le hanno dedicato abbastanza tempo per comunicare e confrontarsi con Lei?
Have your professional(s) used language that you understand (avoided medical jargon, used clear terms)?	Gli operatori sanitari hanno utilizzato un linguaggio comprensibile (hanno evitato un linguaggio medico, utilizzato termini chiari)?

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Have your professional(s) taken into account how you prefer to receive information?	Gli operatori sanitari hanno considerato la modalità con la quale preferisce ricevere le informazioni?
Have you felt that you and your professional(s) had a shared understanding of your disease and treatment?	Ha avuto la sensazione che tra Lei e gli operatori sanitari vi fosse un'intesa comune in merito alla Sua malattia e alla terapia?
My decisions about care and treatment have been respected by my professional(s)	Le mie decisioni in merito all'assistenza e al trattamento sono state rispettate dagli operatori sanitari che mi curano.
I have been given the opportunity to discuss my treatment plan with my professional(s)	Mi è stata data l'opportunità di discutere il mio piano di cura con gli operatori sanitari che mi assistono.
Have you felt satisfied with the care you have received?	È rimasto/a soddisfatto/a delle cure che ha ricevuto?
Have you felt satisfied with the information you have received (e.g. about the disease and its treatment)?	È rimasto/a soddisfatto/a delle informazioni che ha ricevuto (per es. sulla malattia e la terapia)?
During the past 4 weeks:	Durante le ultime quattro settimane:
My medical appointments have interfered with my work / household activities	Gli appuntamenti per le cure e le visite mediche hanno interferito con il mio lavoro/attività domestiche.
My medical appointments have caused problems for my family / carer	Gli appuntamenti per le cure e le visite mediche hanno causato problemi alla mia famiglia e/o alle persone che mi assistono.
<u>How would you rate the services and care organisation of the most recent care you have received, in terms of:</u>	
The provision of follow-up by the different caregivers (doctors, nurses, physiotherapists, psychologists, etc.) after treatment?	Le visite di controllo fornite dai diversi operatori sanitari (medici, infermieri, fisioterapisti, psicologi, ecc.) dopo il trattamento?

4.1.5. English-Danish

Items - English	Danish
<u>We are interested in some things about you and your health. Please answer all of the questions yourself by SELECTING the number that best applies to you. There are no "right" or "wrong" answers.</u>	<u>Vi er interesserede i at vide noget om dig og dit helbred. Vær venlig at besvare alle spørgsmålene selv ved at sætte en ring omkring det svar (tal), som passer bedst på dig. Der er ingen rigtige eller forkerte svar.</u>

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Do you have any trouble doing strenuous activities, like carrying a heavy shopping bag or a suitcase?	Har du nogen vanskeligheder ved at udføre anstrengende aktiviteter, som f.eks. at bære en tung indkøbstaske eller en kuffert?
Do you have any trouble taking a long walk?	Har du nogen vanskeligheder ved at gå en lang tur?
Do you need help caring for your feet (e.g. cutting your toenails)?	Har du brug for hjælp til at pleje dine fødder (f.eks. klippe tånegle)?
Do you have any trouble carrying a heavy bag upstairs?	Har du nogen vanskeligheder ved at bære en tung pose op ad trappe?
Do you have any trouble taking a long walk carrying a heavy pack on your back (e.g. a filled rucksack)?	Har du nogen vanskeligheder ved at gå en lang tur, mens du bærer en tung taske på ryggen (f.eks. en fyldt rygsæk)?
Do you have any trouble taking a short walk outside of the house?	Har du nogen vanskeligheder ved at gå en kort tur udendørs?
Do you need help undressing?	Har du brug for hjælp til at tage tøjet af?
Do you have any trouble walking for 30 min.?	Har du nogen vanskeligheder ved at gå i 30 min.?
During the past week:	I den forløbne uge:
Have you been limited in doing light housework (e.g. dusting or making the bed)?	Har du været begrænset i udførelsen af let husligt arbejde (f.eks. støve af eller rede seng)?
Have you been limited in doing physically demanding recreational activities (e.g., swimming or cycling)?	Har du været begrænset i udførelsen af fysiske fritidsaktiviteter (f.eks. svømning eller cykling)?
Were you limited in doing either your work or other daily activities?	Var du begrænset i udførelsen af enten dit arbejde eller andre daglige aktiviteter?
Have you been limited in doing heavy housework (e.g., washing floors or vacuuming)?	Har du været begrænset i udførelsen af tungt husligt arbejde (f.eks. vaske gulve eller støvsuge)?
Were you limited in pursuing your hobbies or other leisure time activities?	Var du begrænset i at dyrke dine hobbyer eller andre fritidsaktiviteter?
Did pain interfere with your daily activities?	Vanskeliggjorde smerter dine daglige gøremål?
Have you had pain?	Har du haft smerter?
Has pain interfered with your social activities?	Har smerter vanskeliggjort dine sociale aktiviteter?
Has pain made it difficult for you to do the jobs that you usually do around the house?	Har smerter gjort det svært for dig at udføre de opgaver, du plejer at gøre i huset?
Have you had severe pain?	Har du haft svære smerter?
Were you tired?	Har du været træt?
Have you felt weak?	Har du følt dig svag?
Have you felt exhausted?	Har du følt dig udmattet?

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Have you become easily tired?	Er du let blevet træt?
Have you lacked energy?	Har du følt at du manglede energi?
Have you required frequent or long periods of rest?	Har du trængt til hyppige eller lange hvileperioder?
Have you had a feeling of overwhelming and prolonged lack of energy?	Har du haft en følelse af en overvældende og langvarig mangel på energi?
Have you had trouble sleeping?	Har du haft besvær med at sove?
Have you had trouble getting a good night's sleep?	Har du haft besvær med at få en god nats søvn?
Have you had trouble staying asleep?	Har du haft besvær med at blive ved med at sove?
Have you woken up for long periods during the night?	Har du været vågen i lange perioder i løbet af natten?
Have you forced yourself to eat?	Har du tvunget dig selv til at spise?
Have you lacked appetite?	Har du manglet appetit?
Have you lacked interest in eating?	Har du manglet interesse for at spise?
Have you felt nauseated?	Har du haft kvalme?
Have you vomited?	Har du kastet op?
Has nausea or vomiting been a problem for you?	Har kvalme eller opkastning været et problem for dig?
Has nausea or vomiting interfered with your physical activities like taking a walk?	Har kvalme eller opkastning vanskeliggjort fysiske aktiviteter som at gå en tur?
Have you been constipated?	Har du haft forstoppelse?
Have you had stools that were too hard to pass?	Har du haft afføring, som var for hård til, at du kunne komme af med den?
Have your stools been so hard that they were painful to pass?	Har din afføring været så hård, at det gjorde ondt at komme af med den?
Were you short of breath?	Har du haft åndenød?
Did you have severe shortness of breath?	Havde du alvorlig åndenød?
Were you short of breath when walking more than 100 m (100 yds)?	Havde du åndenød, når du gik mere end 100 m?
Were you short of breath when walking less than 100 m (100 yds)?	Havde du åndenød, når du gik mindre end 100 m?
Did you feel tense?	Følte du dig anspændt?
Have you felt vulnerable?	Har du følt dig sårbar?
Have you felt that nothing could cheer you up?	Har du følt, at intet kunne opmuntre dig?
Have you felt miserable?	Har du følt dig elendigt til mode?
Did you feel depressed?	Følte du dig deprimeret?
Did you worry?	Var du bekymret?
Have you felt sad?	Har du følt dig trist?

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Have you been watching yourself closely for any new symptoms?	Har du holdt tæt øje med eventuelle nye symptomer?
To what extent have you been troubled with side-effects from your treatment?	I hvilken grad har du været generet af bivirkninger ved din behandling?
Have you worried about recurrence of your disease?	Har du været bekymret for at din sygdom skal vende tilbage?
Have you been afraid of tumor progression?	Har du været bange for tumor udvikling?
Have you worried about your health in the future?	Har du været bekymret for dit helbred i fremtiden?
How much has your disease been a burden to you?	Hvor meget har din sygdom belastet dig?
Because of your experience with cancer, have you had to limit your life plans or goals?	Har du været nødt til at begrænse dine planer eller mål for livet?
I have felt at peace with myself	Har du følt indre ro?
Have you had difficulty remembering things?	Har du haft svært ved at huske?
Have you had difficulty in concentrating on things, like reading a newspaper or watching television?	Har du haft svært ved at koncentrere dig om ting som f.eks. at læse avis eller se fjernsyn?
Have you been forgetful?	Har du været glemsom?
Have you had difficulty remembering what someone just told you?	Har du haft svært ved at huske, hvad nogen lige fortalte dig?
Have you had difficulty maintaining concentration even when doing something important?	Har du haft svært ved at fastholde koncentrationen, selv når du lavede noget vigtigt?
As a result of your physical condition or medical treatment, have you preferred to spend time alone?	Har du som følge af din fysiske tilstand eller medicinsk behandling foretrukket at være alene?
As a result of your physical condition or medical treatment have you been less able to see your family or friends?	Har du som følge af din fysiske tilstand eller medicinsk behandling haft sværere ved at se familie og venner?
As a result of your physical condition or medical treatment, have you spent less time with your family or friends?	Har du som følge af din fysiske tilstand eller medicinsk behandling brugt mindre tid sammen med familie eller venner?
As a result of your physical condition or medical treatment, have you felt isolated from your family or friends?	Har du som følge af din fysiske tilstand eller medicinsk behandling følt dig isoleret fra familie eller venner?
As a result of your physical condition or medical treatment, have you found it hard to make contact with people?	Har du som følge af din fysiske tilstand eller medicinsk behandling fundet det vanskeligt at tage kontakt til andre mennesker?

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Has your physical condition or medical treatment interfered with your family life?	Har din fysiske tilstand eller medicinske behandling vanskeliggjort dit familieliv?
Has your physical condition or medical treatment interfered with your social activities?	Har din fysiske tilstand eller medicinske behandling vanskeliggjort din omgang med andre mennesker?
Has your physical condition or medical treatment interfered with your relationships with your family or friends?	Har din fysiske tilstand eller medicinsk behandling vanskeliggjort dit forhold til familie eller venner?
Have you been dissatisfied with your physical appearance?	Har du været utilfreds med dit fysiske udseende?
Has the disease or treatment affected your sex life (for the worse)?	Har din sygdom eller behandling påvirket dit sexliv (gjort det dårligere)?
Have you worried about your ability to have children?	Har du været bekymret for din evne til at få børn?
Have you worried that you are a burden to other people	Har du været bekymret for at blive en byrde for andre?
Have you worried about becoming dependent on others?	Har du været bekymret for at blive afhængig af andre?
Has your physical condition or medical treatment caused you financial difficulties?	Har din fysiske tilstand eller medicinske behandling medført økonomiske vanskeligheder for dig?
Has your physical condition or medical treatment caused you financial difficulties leading to changes in your lifestyle?	Har din fysiske tilstand eller medicinske behandling givet dig økonomiske problemer, der har medført ændringer i din livsstil?
As a result of your physical condition or medical treatment, have you had less money to spend on yourself (e.g., for buying yourself something that you would like to have but don't necessarily need)?	Har du, som følge af din fysiske tilstand eller medicinske behandling, haft færre penge at bruge på dig selv (f.eks. til at købe noget til dig selv, som du gerne vil have, men ikke nødvendigvis har brug for)?
As a result of your physical condition or medical treatment, have you had difficulties paying any of your regular expenses (e.g. rent, insurance, phone)?	Har du, som følge af din fysiske tilstand eller medicinske behandling, haft problemer med at betale dine faste udgifter (f.eks. husleje, forsikring, telefon)?
Since the diagnosis and treatment of your cancer: Have you had problems with obtaining insurance, loans, and/or a mortgage?	Siden diagnosticeringen og behandlingen af din kræft: Har du haft problemer med at få forsikring, lån og/eller et realkreditlån?
Since the diagnosis and treatment of your cancer: Have you received support from your employer e.g. arranging flexible working?	Siden diagnosticeringen og behandlingen af din kræft: Har du været tilfreds med den støtte du har modtaget fra din arbejdsgiver fx med at arrangere fleksible arbejdstider?
Since the diagnosis and treatment of your cancer: Have you made positive lifestyle	Siden diagnosticeringen og behandlingen af din kræft: Har du lavet positive ændringer af din livsstil

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changes (e.g., more exercise, healthy food, cutting down smoking)?	(f.eks. mere motion, sund mad, skåret ned på rygning)?
<u>For the following questions please circle the number between 1 and 7 that best applies to you.</u>	<u>For de følgende spørgsmål bedes du vælge et tal mellem 1 og 7</u>
How would you rate your overall quality of life during the past week?	Hvordan vil du vurdere din samlede livskvalitet i den forløbne uge?
How would you rate your overall health during the past week?	Hvordan vil du vurdere dit samlede helbred i den forløbne uge?
Have you had any other significant symptoms or problems that have not been mentioned in the questions above?	Har du haft andre væsentlige symptomer eller problemer, som ikke er nævnt i spørgsmålene ovenfor?
<u>Yes. Please write down the most important ones (up to three), and rate to what extent you have experienced these symptoms or problems during the past week:</u>	<u>Hvis Ja, skriv de vigtigste (højst 3) og angiv i hvilken grad du har haft symptomet eller problemet i den sidste uge:</u>
<u>During the past week, to what extent have you experienced:</u>	<u>Gennem den sidste uge, i hvilken grad har du haft:</u>
Symptom/problem A:	Symptom 1
Symptom/problem B:	Symptom 2
Symptom/problem C:	Symptom 3
<u>We are interested in your MOST RECENT experience of the care you have received and the communication you have had with the professional(s) who treat you.</u>	<u>Vi er interesseret i dine AKTUELLE oplevelser med den pleje du har fået og den kommunikation du har haft med de sundhedsprofessionelle der behandler dig.</u>
Have you been satisfied with your communication with your professional(s)?	Har du været tilfreds med kommunikationen mellem dig og de sundhedsprofessionelle?
Have your professional(s) spent enough time talking with you?	Har du følt at du og de sundhedsprofessionelle, du var i kontakt med, havde en fælles forståelse af din sygdom og din behandling?
Have your professional(s) used language that you understand (avoided medical jargon, used clear terms)?	Hvordan vil du vurdere opfølgning på den pleje/behandling du senest har fået af forskellige sundhedsprofessionelle (læger, sygeplejersker, fysioterapeuter, psykologer osv.)?
Have your professional(s) taken into account how you prefer to receive information?	Har du været tilfreds med den pleje du har fået gennem den sidste uge?
Have you felt that you and your professional(s) had a shared understanding of your disease and treatment?	Har du været tilfreds med den information du har fået gennem den sidste uge (fx om sygdommen og dens behandling)?

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My decisions about care and treatment have been respected by my professional(s)	Mine beslutninger om pleje og behandling er blevet respekteret af mine professionelle
I have been given the opportunity to discuss my treatment plan with my professional(s)	Jeg har fået mulighed for at diskutere min behandlingsplan med mine fagpersoner
Have you felt satisfied with the care you have received?	Har du været tilfreds med den behandling, du har fået?
Have you felt satisfied with the information you have received (e.g. about the disease and its treatment)?	Har du været tilfreds med de oplysninger, du har fået (fx om sygdommen og behandlingen)?
During the past 4 weeks:	
My medical appointments have interfered with my work / household activities	Mine lægeaftaler har forstyrret mit arbejde/husholdningsaktiviteter
My medical appointments have caused problems for my family / carer	Mine lægeaftaler har forårsaget problemer for min familie/plejer
<u>How would you rate the services and care organisation of the most recent care you have received, in terms of:</u>	<u>Hvordan vil du vurdere ydelserne og plejeorganiseringen af den seneste pleje, du har modtaget i forhold til:</u>
The provision of follow-up by the different caregivers (doctors, nurses, physiotherapists, psychologists, etc.) after treatment?	Har du haft nogen yderligere vigtige symptomer eller problemer, som ikke er blevet nævnt i spørgsmålene ovenfor? (Have you had any additional, important symptoms or problems that have not been mentioned in the questions above?)

5. References

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